

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Return Programmes and Diaspora/Migrant Organizations: Projections and Realities

Research Digest (WP7)

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Abstract

This study critically examines the tensions between state-led return migration policies and the responses of diaspora/migrant organizations (DO/MOs) in Sweden and Germany. While policymakers increasingly frame diasporas as “key partners” in facilitating voluntary returns, empirical evidence reveals a stark disconnect between policy rhetoric and DO/MOs’ realities. Through inductive analysis of interviews with migrant-led organizations, we identify *five discursive patterns* shaping engagement: *disengagement*, *conditional support*, *pragmatic acceptance*, *alignment (with criminal deportations)*, and *direct opposition*. These positions reflect ethical dilemmas, structural constraints, and strategic negotiations within an increasingly securitized migration landscape

Key findings include:

- The evidence of policy initiatives in both Sweden and Germany highlights a gap between the intended policy objectives and the actual experiences encountered in mobilising diaspora organisations for development and return policies. Despite institutional frameworks such as the EU’s Global Diaspora Facility (EUDiF) and national strategies, concrete connections between diaspora engagement and return policies remain unclear. Efforts to link diaspora engagement with return and readmission policies—such as programmes and projects aimed at inviting diaspora organisations—are still ambiguous and lack concrete results. Initiatives are often ad hoc, underfunded, or misaligned with diaspora priorities.
- Migrant and diaspora communities are increasingly concerned about the growing politicisation of migration issues, the anti-refugee stance, and the pro-deportation discourse in both countries, which in turn influences their discursive and behavioural patterns. They are navigating an “ontological mismatch” that arises out of contradictions from the involvement in return-related activities with the foundational principles of many MO/DOs that prioritize integration and transnational protection issues.
- Diaspora organizations have different perceptions about returns (both voluntary and involuntary) and discursive positions, as well as differentiated practices in their engagement with return policies and development work. This study identifies five discursive positions: *disengagement*, *conditional support*, *pragmatic acceptance*, *alignment (with criminal deportations)*, and *direct opposition*. These diverse responses reflect tensions between state objectives and migrant communities’ lived experiences, with many organizations focusing on integration or transnational development, not on return facilitation. Many MO/DO representatives interviewed show little interest in the topic of return and do not engage in any related activities or policies, which we try to capture by describing a discursive pattern of *disengagement*.

Keywords: Diasporas, diaspora organisations, return policies, return governance

1. Introduction

The term "diaspora" broadly encompasses immigrant populations, displaced communities, and transnational networks - concepts that have evolved to reflect increasingly complex social formations shaped by migration and globalization. When employing this terminology, it is crucial to distinguish between scholarly conceptualizations and those emerging from political or policy discourses.

Within academia, diaspora studies have undergone significant theoretical development over the past three decades. Early scholarship adopted an essentialist framework, characterizing diasporas as homogeneous entities bound by shared identity narratives rooted in collective trauma and displacement (Butler 2001; Cohen & Fischer, 2019). This paradigm frequently emphasized an enduring connection to—and desire to return to—a tangible or imagined homeland, as exemplified by classical cases like the Palestinian diaspora.

Contemporary scholarship, however, has moved beyond these rigid categorizations. Current approaches recognize diaspora identities as inherently diverse, dynamic, and subject to continuous renegotiation (Anas 2022; Ardovini 2022). This shift reflects broader theoretical engagements with transnationalism, hybridity, and the fluid nature of belonging in an interconnected world. As a result, multiple diasporas of one country of origin can be identified in any host society context¹ in addition to their transnational relations across multiple host society contexts. The primary differences among communities from the same country of origin include various 'generations' and arrival timelines, often linked to political events in their homeland, reflecting differing political views - sometimes opposing. There are also varying degrees of politicization, frequently connected to the desire for representation of all individuals from their country of origin within the host society. Additionally, factors such as place of residence, socio-economic status, skills, generation, and class come into play. Some scholars suggest completely abandoning the term 'diaspora,' while others note that it has increasingly been adopted by individuals from abroad as a form of self-identification (Cohen & Fischer, 2019).

In contrast to scholarly conceptualizations, mainstream public and policy discourses often employ an undifferentiated understanding of diaspora. The International Organization for Migration (IOM), for instance, defines diasporas broadly as "*transnational communities comprising individuals connected to multiple countries or societies, including migrants and their descendants who share a sense of collective identity and belonging*" (IOM, 2013, p. 1). Notably, the IOM suggests that prolonged displacement may transform refugee populations into diasporic communities.

This simplified policy framing serves strategic purposes. As Horst (2013, p. 231) observes, the diaspora concept gains its political potency precisely through its capacity to "*ignore internal group differences and function as a rallying call*" (cf. Dufoix, 2008). Such operational definitions enable institutions to engage diasporas as coherent policy targets, with contemporary humanitarian frameworks increasingly positioning them as key transnational actors (DRC, 2024). This instrumental approach, while analytically reductive, reflects the evolving priorities of governance and aid organizations seeking to mobilize diasporic networks for development and crisis response.

¹ For an elaborate discussion on the trajectory of diaspora studies, see Meininghaus & Mielke, 2019, pp. 9-11.

DIASPORAS AND THEIR CONTRIBUTIONS: A snapshot of the available evidence

KEY POINTS

- IOM defines diasporas as migrants or descendants of migrants whose identity and senses of belonging, either real or symbolic, have been shaped by their migration experience and background (see Figure 1).
- At least **280,5 million people** – around 3 per cent of the global population - live in a country other than their country of origin.
- More than **70 percent** of countries participating in the Migration Governance Indicators (MGI) globally have established diaspora or emigration institutions.
- **One in three** MGI countries globally engages its diaspora in agenda setting and implementation of development policy.
- **Two thirds** of countries globally accepted dual citizenship.
- Migrants are estimated to generate **9.4 percent of the global GDP**.
- Migrants often **retain connections** to their families and friends back home, send them part of their income or savings through remittances, share knowledge and skills acquired in migration and engage in trade, entrepreneurship and investment. Migrant children often retain ties to their parents' countries of origin, as well. Senses of belonging of migrant descendants, however, can become weaker over time.
- Worldwide, there are more than **200,000 diaspora and migrant organizations**.
- The **Global Compact for Migration** and the **Dublin Declaration** recognize diasporas as development and humanitarian partners.

Figure 1: Definition of diaspora

Figure 1 - IOMs Thematic Brief Issue nr 3 | July 2023

“Diaspora engagement” policies and programs have become increasingly popular as a development strategy, particularly since the early 2000s (Newland, 2022). Diasporas are approached as ‘agents of development’ for their home countries (EC, 2005), considering that their financial and social remittances² that contribute to the development and the transfer of capital, skills, and expertise occur upon the migrants’ return that is assumed to be voluntary and often after the completion of the migration journey such as in retirement.

As return and readmission policies increasingly play a crucial role in migration control, influencing host states in Europe and North America and their relationships with origin country authorities, it is important to explore how the return-diaspora connection develops. To our knowledge, there are few studies indicating that coerced returns become politically significant in origin country-diaspora relations, as promoting legal emigration channels and preventing the forced return of emigrants are essential policy interests for origin countries (Adam et al. 2020). Less is understood about how diasporas perceive the growing emphasis on coerced returns by destination countries and their interactions with both origin and destination countries regarding this issue.

² The World Bank estimates that the 2022 personal remittance flows to low- and middle-income countries amounted to 647 billion USD, continuing to outpace the flows of official development aid, foreign investment, and other financial capital flows. However, informal transfers continue to range between 35 to 75 percent of formal transfers, accounting to 280-600 billion USD based on latest data. Combined formal and informal remittance transfers could therefore account to 1 trillion USD - a significant financing opportunity for transnational families and communities (IOM – Thematic Brief - Issue nr 3, July 2023). https://www.migrationdataportal.org/sites/g/files/tmzbd1251/files/2023-09/GDI%20Briefs_Diaspora_210923.pdf

Although potential relations between coerced returns and diaspora policies have not been yet studied in depth, there is a rich scholarly and grey literature on diasporas` engagement with development cooperation policy fields in both host/donor countries and countries of origin (IOM 2013; 2018; World Bank 2006; Orozco 2022). However, the specific role intended for diasporas in current initiatives—such as programs, projects, policies, partnerships, and agreements aimed at facilitating returns—remains unclear. Our understanding of how the policies and perspectives of host states have evolved in response to these initiatives is limited. One critical area that warrants further investigation is the role of migrant/diaspora organizations (MO/DOs). These groups are increasingly recognized as vital contributors to development efforts in their countries of origin and are expected to play some role in returns, such as creating conducive conditions for return in the origin country or contributing pre-return preparations such as return counselling.

The terms “migrant” and “diaspora organization”, which are similar to “immigrant” or “refugee” organization, are subjects of debate. While both terms are still frequently used, they are also heavily criticized for various reasons, including the difficulties in determining who qualifies as a migrant and the focus of organizational activities (home versus host country). Moreover, these terms are not always used by the organizations themselves, which might externally be labelled MO and/or DOs. We recognize that this category should be defined by the organizations themselves. The various definitions, often shaped by the context of the host country, can lead to significant challenges. For the sake of this digest, we use the term migrant/diaspora organizations (MO/DOs). For our working definition, MO/DOs are non-profit organisations or initiatives run by individuals with migration backgrounds in their country of residence. We do not view registration as a requirement for being classified as MO/DOs to cover both formal and informal network-type organisational forms. Our focus is on MO/DOs that pursue objectives and engage in actions to form a distinct diaspora group as well as activities linked to their community country of origin, specifically aimed at offering support for development, reconstruction, emergency relief, human rights, and capacity building for civil society advocacy as well as some activities targeting immigrant communities in countries of settlement.³

This research digest takes this working definition as a starting point. The aim is to enhance the understanding of the various roles that MO/DOs play, examining both how policymakers envision these roles and how they are practiced in reality. As we concentrate on diaspora organizations and their involvement in a new area of focus—return—the concept of “invited/invented spaces” (Rother, 2022; Miraftab, 2004, Mencutek 2020, Barthoma 2024) provides a valuable perspective. Invited spaces refer to formal channels created by states for civil society engagement, with civil society actors being guests instead of hosts. Conversely, invented places provide an arena where civil society organizations possess autonomy (Rother, 2022, p. 5) and challenge the status-quo (Miraftab, 2004). This framework helps us understand how and to what extent MOs/DOs organizations (are invited to) participate in return policies and practices, whether they support/align, oppose, or disengage from them. Earlier studies adopting the invented/invited space framework explored the engagements of refugee-led community organisations (RCOs) and showed that RCOs, by and large, carve out

³ There is also terminology of transnational migrant organizations (TMOs). They have effects on social spaces in countries of origin, transit and arrival. They are relevant for managing remittances, act as instruments or outcomes of social movements, work in humanitarian crises, organize interest representation and claims-making and (re)produce feelings of belonging. See Pries & Günzel, 2024.

a space of influence through civic activism in the migration architectures of receiving countries (Mencuttek, 2020). RCOs become vital in the refugees' search for means to alleviate the sufferings of their fellows, to empower their community and claim rights for an improvement of their conditions. Increasing numbers of formal and informal (registered or not registered) RCOs operate in the invited spaces opened by the state agencies and international donors. Only rarely, however, are RCOs able to invent spaces to challenge existing power relations (Mencuttek, 2020). It could be interesting to reflect on whether the invented and invited spaces theoretical framework helps us to explain (if there is) MO/DOs' engagement with the return migration infrastructure⁴ in host countries, which is particularly targeting irregular migrants/refugees and development projects in the origin country.

This research digest presents a comparative empirical analysis of diaspora engagement policies in Sweden and Germany, addressing two central research questions:

1. How do Swedish and German authorities conceptualize the role of migrant/diaspora organizations (MO/DOs) within return migration governance, diaspora policies, and development cooperation—particularly regarding both voluntary and coerced return programs?
2. How do MO/DOs position themselves vis-à-vis these state policies, and what factors (e.g., ethical, pragmatic, or survival considerations) shape their responses?

Employing the theoretical lenses of the "invited/invented spaces" framework, the analysis interrogates the mechanisms through which state actors *invite* MO/DO participation into return governance, and explores how MO/DOs navigate, resist, or reinterpret these invitations to *invent* discursive and operational spaces aligned with their own priorities. This dual lens reveals the contested terrain of return migration governance, where formal policy designs intersect with grassroots organizational strategies.

To answer these questions, we begin by situating our discussion within the broader scholarly debates on migration and development, particularly focusing on how diasporas are conceptualized as key actors in these processes. Against this backdrop, we will examine how diaspora engagement is framed within global migration governance, particularly in policy documents such as those produced by the EU, IOM, and the Global Compact for Safe, Orderly, and Regular Migration. These frameworks often promote diaspora involvement as a win-win scenario, where migrants contribute to their countries of origin while destination countries manage migration flows more effectively. However, critical perspectives question whether these policies genuinely empower diasporas or instead co-opt them into mechanisms of migration control, particularly in the context of return and readmission agreements.

To explore these dynamics in practice, we will analyse two case studies: Sweden and Germany, both of which have active diaspora engagement policies alongside structured return migration programs. In both cases, we will investigate how state actors envision the role of diaspora organizations—whether as co-producers of policy, implementers, or advocates—and how these expectations align or conflict with the actual practices and perceptions of diaspora groups themselves.

⁴ See further Sweden and Germany WP3 reports on return infrastructures. Available at: www.returnmigration.eu

2. Methodology

Our analysis draws on a combination of policy documents, reports from governmental and non-governmental organizations, and, where applicable, interviews with diaspora representatives and policymakers in Sweden and Germany. This mixed-method approach allows us to compare institutional narratives with on-the-ground realities, shedding light on the tensions between policy intentions and diaspora organizations' agency. By centring the voices of diaspora organizations, we aim to move beyond top-down policy analyses and instead explore how these groups navigate, resist, or reshape the frameworks imposed upon them.

In Sweden, data collection involved semi-structured interviews with 12 representatives from migrant-led diaspora organizations, capturing a diverse range of perspectives. Participants included two representatives from umbrella migrant organizations (n=2), six (n=6) from migrant-led associations (with some individuals representing multiple roles), and three (n=3) from group-specific organizations, (faith-based migrant organization, migrant family organisation, or academic networks). Additionally, an activist specializing in migrants' rights and return policies, as well as a case officer from the Swedish Migration Agency responsible for voluntary repatriation, provided further insights. These interviews were supplemented by an analysis of government directives, policy frameworks, and academic literature. The research aimed to explore how diaspora organizations perceive and engage with return policies, as well as the challenges they encounter in navigating these dynamics.

Focusing specifically on Iraqi and Turkish diaspora communities, the study sought to account for variations based on migration waves (long-settled versus newly arrived), gender, faith-based affiliations, and minority or ideological distinctions. This approach ensured a nuanced understanding of how different subgroups within these diasporas interact with return policies and the broader migration governance framework.

In Germany, data were primarily gathered through purposive snowball sampling, which included 28 interviews and several informal discussions. The interviewees encompassed representatives from four migrant umbrella organizations (n=4), eleven immigrant organizations (n=11), three community initiative members, one activist from an anti-deportation movement (n=1), a representative from Germany's newly formed Refugee Advisory Board⁵ (n=1), two researchers who performed a mapping study on immigrant organizations (n=2), and refugees engaged in community initiatives. Additionally, five meetings were held with policy advisors and coordinators focused on diaspora-migration programs, attended by one to three advisors from various units. Researchers put specific attention to accessing Syrian and Afghan diaspora organizations, as they are two groups particularly important (politically salient) in the German political landscape as of early 2025 (regime change in Syria in December 2024, incidents involving Afghan rejected asylum seekers; the election and coalition talks where migration control has salience). We interviewed six Syrian and 11 Afghan organizations/initiatives.

⁵ The Refugee Advisory Board (GER-RAB) aims to anchor the participation of refugees in Germany's engagement with the international refugee system, particularly in the context of future German delegations at international and regional meetings on forced migration. For further information see <https://www.bicc.de/Header%20Topics/Call%20for%20applications%20%20%20Refugee%20Advisory%20Board%20for%20Germany%20%28GER-RAB%29>.

Approaching migrant organizations in Sweden and Germany for a study on return proved to be a significant challenge. We received mixed reactions from the stakeholders we contacted, some of which were very negative. Several organizations outright refused to participate in a study focused on returns, while others cancelled and rescheduled interviews several times. Despite the researchers' efforts to clearly explain the purpose of the study - both in writing and verbally - as an exploration of voluntary and forced returns, many interviewees seemed confused or uncomfortable with the topic. This was in stark contrast to the researchers' previous experience conducting studies on asylum, reception, and integration, where such resistance was not present. This change in response can be attributed to changing political contexts and the fact that the topic of "returns", even when prefixed with "voluntary", carries a deeply negative connotation for many migrant stakeholders.

These considerations highlight the importance of self-reflexivity in methodological design, especially when studying sensitive issues such as returns. The challenges we encountered in the field underscore the need for researchers to critically examine their positionality, the broader socio-political context, and the potential impact of their research on the communities they study. Two of the authors' positionality as an immigrant in Germany and Sweden provided very limited easiness in accessing Turkey originated diaspora organizations. The other author's long-term experience in the field of Afghanistan studies facilitated access and trust of Afghan diaspora organizations in Germany. Rather than taking issue with the donor, in this case EU, the topic was found less attractive and highly sensitive to reflect on by MO/DOS.

For the analysis, all interviews were audio-recorded and subsequently transcribed to ensure accuracy and facilitate detailed analysis. The transcribed data were then systematically coded and thematically analysed in MAXQDA. Using a combination of deductive and inductive coding approaches, the data were categorized into key themes such as "policy implementation challenges", "diaspora engagement", "approach to returns", and "capacity constraints". MAXQDA's tools enabled the identification of patterns and relationships within the data, providing a robust foundation for understanding the perspectives and experiences of all stakeholders involved.

3. Scholarly Discussions and Global Policy Context

This section begins by situating our analysis within broader academic debates on migration and development, with particular attention to discussions around the diasporas' role. We then analyse how diaspora engagement frameworks have been institutionalized within global migration governance architectures, paying specific attention to their articulation in global compacts. Subsequently, we undertake a comparative policy analysis of Sweden and Germany as illustrative case studies. While both national contexts formally recognize diasporas' developmental potential, our examination reveals significant ambiguities in how this recognition translates into concrete policy mechanisms linking diaspora engagement with return migration and readmission arrangements.

3.1. Discussions on Migration Development Nexus and Diaspora engagement in Migration

The migration-development nexus has been a topic of research in migration studies and policy alike, positing that human mobility can generate positive developmental outcomes for both sending and receiving countries. Early scholarship predominantly emphasized financial

remittances as the primary mechanism linking migration to development (World Bank, 2006). Subsequent theoretical advancements expanded this framework to include knowledge transfer, entrepreneurship, and institutional reforms facilitated by diasporas (Kuznetsov, 2010; Saxenian, 2008). It is assumed that skilled expatriates and “returnee entrepreneurs” (Riaño, 2022) returning home can reduce skill mismatches and stimulate economic growth (Sinatti & Horst, 2015). This conceptual evolution reflects the emergence of analytical categories such as social and political remittances, which collectively underpin the “triple win” scenario, which envisions returns as benefits for the origin, destination country, and migrants themselves.

However, critical scholarship challenges these optimistic assumptions by highlighting three key limitations: (1) limitations due to the non-linear, multi-directional nature of transnational practices (Castles, 2008); (2) contextual contingencies shaping return outcomes (King, 2022) and, (3) the frequent conflation of voluntary and forced return dynamics in policy formulations. These critiques reveal fundamental tensions between theoretical constructs and empirical realities in migration-development relationships.

Another strand of research focuses on diaspora engagement policies. Governments in sending countries have developed sophisticated apparatuses, ranging from dedicated ministries (Gamlen, 2014) to hybrid directorates (Tittel-Mosser, 2023), employing strategies such as “co-development” initiatives and diaspora leveraging programmes which aim at not only mobilising diaspora communities to support the development and foreign policy objectives of their home countries, but also controlling their expatriate populations (Wackenhut, 2022; Brand, 2006). Policy objectives in some origin countries have shifted from remittances towards a more comprehensive engagement with the diaspora community. Diaspora engagement policies often emphasize tapping into diaspora resources (e.g., remittances, investments) or embracing the diaspora as a symbol of national identity (Bauböck, 2009; Gamlen, 2014). Critics argue that these efforts sometimes serve migration control agendas rather than genuine development goals (De Haas, 2006). Origin country governments’ interest in engaging with their diasporas and gleaning the economic benefits of return or remittances are typically focused on voluntary returns of those with capital, but rarely on (nor are they supportive of), the forced return of their nationals.

3.2 European Commission, International Organization of Migration and Global Compacts: Global Policy Emphasis on Diasporas as Development Actor

The European Commission (EC) has progressively institutionalized the diaspora-as-agent paradigm since its 2005 Communication on Migration and Development, which explicitly framed diasporas as “important potential actor[s] in the development of countries of origin” (EC, 2005, p. 6). The EC suggested that Member States identify and engage diaspora organisations, which could be suitable and representative interlocutors in development policy and/or possible initiators of development projects in countries of origin (EC, 2005, p.7)⁶. This policy trajectory has evolved through several key initiatives. For example, the EC’s 2011

⁶ Interesting points that as early as 2005, the Commission promised to “look at how to ensure that the residence rights in the EU of diaspora members who decide to engage in such activities are not affected by temporary returns to countries of origin” (EC, 2005, p. 8) and “joint projects by diaspora organisations – preferably from two or more Member States – and local organisations interested in supporting local development.” (EC, 2005, p. 26).

document reinforced “diasporas as actors of country of origin development” (EC, 2011). In the same document, it is noted that “Diaspora-related issues are also mainstreamed into the migration and development items of the political dialogues with partner countries, for instance in the context of the Prague process, the EU Africa Migration, Mobility and Employment Partnership, the EU-ACP dialogue and the EU-LAC migration dialogue” (EC, 2011, p.4). Another milestone in this trajectory, is the establishment of the EU’s Global Diaspora Facility (EUDiF) in 2019, which entrusted the International Centre for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD) to enhance diaspora engagement for development in EU partner countries.

Another driving actor of the diaspora engagement agenda has been the IOM, particularly through initiatives like the 2013 Diaspora Ministerial Conference. The IOM's core message was that “diasporas can build bridges between states and societies”, advocating for strategies to harness this potential. The IOM's tripartite strategy - focused on potential realization, effective engagement, and empowerment (IOM, 2013, p. 1) - reflects an institutional commitment to diaspora-centred development, albeit with notable omissions regarding return migration in formal policy documents. IOM’s diverse diaspora engagement programs have received funding from the IOM Development Fund at the request of Member States with significant diaspora communities overseas. Among objectives and areas of activity regarding diaspora, return has not been directly mentioned in the diaspora-related policy papers of IOM.

The preparation for the Global Compact for Migration (GCM) gave momentum to the activities on diaspora, such as IOM online Platform named *iDiaspora Forum*⁷ and onsite high-level diaspora forums, organized in partnership with the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe (Forum 2018)⁸. The GCM includes extensive references to diaspora as part of both the whole-of-society approach and the whole-of-government approach.

With the whole-of-society approach, GCM positioned diasporas alongside civil society and private sector actors, including local communities, academia, parliamentarians, trade unions, national human rights institutions, the media, and other relevant stakeholders in migration governance. With the whole-of-government approach, the GCM highlighted the importance of a cross-sectoral approach to develop and implement effective migration policies and practices, which in turn requires horizontal and vertical policy coherence across all sectors and levels of government (GCM, 2018, p. 6).

Objective 19 of the GCM explicitly aims to “Create conditions for migrants and diasporas to fully contribute to sustainable development in all countries” (GCM, 2018, p. 28), while the Global Compact on Refugees recommends diaspora inclusion “where relevant” (UNHCR, 2018, p. 14). These frameworks establish normative expectations that both Germany and Sweden have sought to operationalise, albeit with significant challenges in reconciling diaspora engagement with return governance regimes, as our subsequent analysis demonstrates.

⁷ See [Forums | iDiaspora](#). iDiaspora is a global engagement and knowledge exchange hub for diaspora communities and those looking to engage with them. It provides comprehensive, regularly updated data and analysis relevant to diaspora communities, policy makers, NGO actors, and showcases successful diaspora actions and partnerships.

⁸ Forum 2018. <https://www.idiaspora.org/en/connect/get-inspired/highlights-annual-diaspora-forum-may-2018>

4. Case Studies

4.1. Sweden: Diaspora Engagement in Return and Development Projects

Until recently the Swedish government did not explicitly define “diaspora engagement” as a core component of its return and readmission policies. However, diaspora communities are recognized for their role in integration and development efforts, particularly through migration and development cooperation programs led by the Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency (Sida). The Swedish Migration Agency (*Migrationsverket-SMA*) primarily focuses on integration and reintegration support for returned migrants on an individual level, with diaspora engagement more commonly associated with development cooperation rather than return policies.

However, this development-oriented policy changed with the introduction of a new migration strategy by the new government. In 2024, the Swedish government adopted a new *Strategy for Global Development Cooperation on Migration, Returns, and Voluntary Repatriation (2024–2028)*.⁹ This strategy emphasizes the role of diaspora organizations in promoting sustainable reintegration and strengthening local capacity and infrastructure in countries prioritized for returns. Key interventions include providing access to identification, legal documentation, employment opportunities and psychosocial support. The strategy emphasizes the need for coherence between Sweden's development assistance and migration policies, promoting synergies that facilitate voluntary return and sustainable reintegration (Government of Sweden, 2024). In response, Sida has developed its own *Activity Strategy (2024-2026)*, which emphasizes the importance of strengthening synergies between development assistance and migration policies. The strategy highlights the role of development cooperation in addressing the root causes of irregular migration and forced displacement, and in promoting safe, orderly and regular migration. The strategy also emphasizes the need for innovative approaches to harness the positive contributions of returning migrants to the development of partner countries (Sida, 2024). In a letter responding to the government directive (UD2021/18787), Sida outlined its efforts to support safe, orderly, and regulated migration through 47 initiatives funded with approximately 813 million SEK between 2018 and 2023. These initiatives focus on strengthening the capacity of partner countries to manage migration, promote voluntary return, and facilitate sustainable reintegration (Sida, 2023).

A pivotal document delineating the fundamental components of the ‘new’ migration policy is the *Policy Framework for Civil Society* (Government of Sweden, 2023). This framework document advocates for collaborative endeavours between Swedish civil society organizations, diaspora groups, and international actors, with the objective of attaining the Sustainable Development Goals. It mirrors Sweden's broader acknowledgement of diaspora organizations as pivotal entities in both the process of migrant integration and the development of their respective countries of origin (Government of Sweden, 2023).

In accordance with this novel policy strategy, the Swedish government has explicitly charged the SMA with the objective of enhancing its efforts to promote voluntary returns. In its appropriation letter for the 2024 fiscal year, the government mandated the SMA to bolster its informational efforts concerning return migration prospects, to collaborate with pertinent

⁹ [New strategy for Sweden's global development cooperation on migration, returns and voluntary repatriation - Government.se](https://www.government.se/press-releases/2024/04/new-strategy-for-sweden-s-global-development-cooperation-on-migration-returns-and-voluntary-repatriation)

authorities, and to establish a dialogue and cooperation with diaspora groups and civil society organizations to raise awareness of repatriation opportunities (Letter of Government Regulation for the 2024 fiscal year regarding the Migration Agency, pp. 3–4). For the 2025 financial year, the SMA was further directed to cooperate with relevant authorities and interested parties to reach individuals eligible for repatriation grants under Ordinance (1984:890) and to raise awareness of repatriation possibilities (*Letter of Government Regulation for the 2025 financial year regarding the Swedish Migration Agency*, pp. 3–4). These directives underscore the Swedish government's pragmatic approach to leveraging diaspora networks for the management of migration and the realization of development objectives.

To integrate Swedish development assistance with broader migration and return frameworks, the Swedish Government further proposed that development assistance be made conditional, contingent upon recipient countries' adherence to international law and cooperation on readmission agreements, including the issuance of travel documents (Government of Sweden, 2024). This policy shift has drawn strong reactions, particularly from civil society organizations (CSOs) operating in the development and humanitarian aid sectors. These reactions have highlighted concerns regarding the use of development aid to finance objectives related to migration policy. For instance, ForumCiv criticized the government's strategy, arguing that its emphasis on deterring migration to Sweden and facilitating deportations undermines the objective of combating poverty and oppression (ForumCiv, 2024). Similarly, CONCORD Sweden highlighted that forced deportations and conditional aid violate OECD-DAC principles, which prohibit the use of aid to pressure countries into accepting returnees (CONCORD Sweden, 2023).

Despite Sweden's acknowledgement of diaspora communities in the context of development cooperation, as evidenced by initiatives such as the *DiasporaLink* Program and *Migration and Development Cooperation*, along with the recent emphasis on diaspora organizations in the Government's appropriation letters to the SMA, their role in return and readmission policies remains less explicitly delineated. Their involvement in Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) programs and reintegration efforts remains limited. The primary policy framework for diaspora engagement is delineated in Sida's Activity Strategy (2024–2026) and bilateral strategies for priority countries. These strategies accentuate the development potential of diaspora communities but do not explicitly link them to return policies.

4.1.1. Swedish Government's Approach to Returns: Policy Expectations vs. Realities

The Swedish government's recent emphasis on return migration as part of its “new” migration governance strategy aligns with a broader European trend in migration policy, where the focus has shifted toward reducing migrant populations through voluntary and, at times, forced returns. This approach, however, is not without its complexities and contradictions. As previously discussed, two consecutive appropriation letters from the government to the Migration Agency include the SMA's mandate to raise awareness of voluntary repatriation possibilities through collaboration with diaspora organizations and civil society actors. As an SMA officer noted, the SMA has provided project support for over a decade to associations working on repatriation preparations. This support has included initiatives such as providing vocational training and business start-ups in countries of origin (SMA-1, 2025). However, the implementation of these directives frequently exhibits a lack of clarity and long-term planning,

resulting in discrepancies between expectations and outcomes. As an SMA officer noted, *“I receive appropriation letters annually; these are not long-term funding commitments, and financial resources are allocated differently from year to year for repatriation efforts”* (SMA-1, 2025).

The Swedish government's strategy of engaging diaspora organizations and civil society actors as key partners in promoting voluntary repatriation is intended to leverage their cultural and social capital to reach “hard-to-reach” migrant groups. However, this strategy often operates within a top-down framework that fails to consider the capacity, willingness, and perspectives of these organizations. As one respondent noted, *“It's so clear that the Migration Agency doesn't even have the resources to do what they have to do”* (MigS-1). The result is a significant disconnect between policy intentions and on-the-ground realities, exacerbated by resource constraints, political pressures, and pervasive myths surrounding return migration. As the same respondent noted, having worked for many years in a civil society organization (CSO) providing legal support to asylum seekers and irregular migrants, *“there are a lot of myths circulating both within authorities but also in society in general”* (MigS-1). These myths engender unrealistic expectations regarding the feasibility of voluntary returns and the conditions in origin countries.

Policymakers frequently presume that migrants will readily accept return offers when provided with financial incentives, and that such return migration automatically translates into development. This can be regarded as a *top-down myopia* which reduces complex return dynamics to simplistic economic transactions. Embedded within this line of thought lies the problematic presupposition that transnational diaspora networks are automatically inclined and operationally equipped to intermedicate return migration. However, interviews with migrant stakeholders reveal a more nuanced reality. Many migrant stakeholders that we interviewed are sceptical of government policies and lack the expertise or resources to participate in any type of return-related projects. This scepticism is compounded by the circulation of myths surrounding return grants and reintegration support, which create unrealistic expectations among both migrants and authorities. For example, while the promise of financial incentives and business start-up support may sound appealing, the reality is often far more complicated, with stringent eligibility criteria and limited access to meaningful opportunities. As one respondent pointed out, *“There are a lot of myths circulating... you can get money and help to start a business, but virtually no one has received this because there are like 1000 different requirements that must be met”* (MigS-1). The myths surrounding returns not only mislead migrants but also perpetuate a false narrative that voluntary returns are a straightforward solution to complex migration challenges.

Another aspect that our respondents highlighted is the repercussions of the shifting political climate in Sweden. They noted that the rise of right-wing parties in Swedish politics has led to the intensification of crisis-driven narratives that frame migration as a problem to be solved through returns rather than through inclusive integration efforts. This shift in political priorities has resulted in the dismantling of integration programs and a greater emphasis on deportation and forced returns. As one respondent noted, *“Since the new government took office, integration work has been dismantled”* (MigS-2). The new government's prioritization of returns has come at the expense of integration work, creating an exclusionary discourse that undermines the rights and dignity of migrants. This political environment not only shapes public perceptions of migration but also influences policy formulation, often prioritizing short-term solutions over long-term strategies that address the root causes of migration.

Criticising the government's obsession about "returns", one respondent noted: "*All the money that Sweden spends on trying to get people to leave... if you put those resources into actually getting people to get a good start here instead, I think it would give Sweden a lot more in the long run*" (MigS-1).

In an effort to elucidate the underlying principles of this policy formulation, we conducted interviews with policy case officers at the SMA. We inquired about their plans for implementing the policy as outlined in the Government's 2024 appropriation letter to the SMA, and the measures they have taken thus far to achieve this objective. However, the respondents offered only limited information on the subject, citing previous initiatives and procedures for "voluntary repatriation". This led us to analyse the policy as an experimental governance initiative, framed within a 'whole-of-government' approach that implicitly expects CSOs (including migrant groups) to harmonize their actions with state policy objectives. This perspective aligns with Miraftab's (2009) concept of "invited spaces", which emphasizes the role of invitation in shaping participation. However, it is important to note that this policy has not been widely understood by migrant stakeholders. In our interviews with them, we often found ourselves as the primary source of information regarding this policy. This led us to focus instead more on their views about forced and 'voluntary' returns.

4.1.2. Diaspora Migrant Organizations' Approach to Returns: Turkish and Iraqi Diasporas

Sweden has a vibrant and diverse landscape of diaspora and migrant organizations (DMOs), reflecting its history of immigration and multicultural society. These organizations serve various functions, including integration, cultural preservation, advocacy, development cooperation, and youth empowerment. Their activities range from local community-building to transnational engagement with countries of origin. We could not find the total number of active migrant/diaspora organizations, however, for example, Sweden has 133 Afghan diaspora organizations, the highest per capita among European countries (DRC, 2019). Among the migrant groups, Somalis are well organized in development projects, such as the Somali Diaspora Alliance fostering youth engagement.

development. While some focus on integration, cultural preservation and advocacy, others engage in transnational development, youth empowerment, and policy influence. The high number of Afghan organizations compared to other European countries highlights Sweden's unique position as a hub for diaspora activism. Looking at their focus areas, we can argue that the large majority of MOs work to support migrants in Swedish society, offering language courses, mentorship, and networking opportunities. There are also MOs who has stronger advocacy goal concerning the developments in their country of origin (e.g., Assyrians, Kurds). There are also umbrella organizations like Center for Local Development and the Diaspora (CLDD)¹⁰, focus on diaspora contributions to global development and voluntary repatriation. Sweden's diaspora organizations play a crucial role in both local integration and global

The landscape of DO/MOS in Sweden is deeply intertwined with the country's historical embrace of multiculturalism and its Nordic tradition of popular movements (*folkrörelser*). Since the 1970s, the Swedish state has systematically institutionalized support for ethnically based civil society organizations, creating a framework that simultaneously enables and constrains migrant communities' organizational agency (Hammar, 1985). This institutional

¹⁰ <https://cldd.se/about-us/>

development reflects broader political debates about diversity's role in Sweden's social-democratic welfare state (Borevi, 2004; Schierup, 1991).

Sweden's framework for immigrant organizations (SIOs) has evolved significantly over time. In the 1970s and 1980s, the government actively encouraged the formation of national associations (*riksförbund*), which served as umbrella groups for migrant communities - from Finns and Yugoslavs to Kurds and Assyrians. These organizations were incorporated into a corporatist system under the Swedish National Board of Immigration (*Statens Invandrarverk*, SIV), which provided funding but also exerted oversight, ensuring that SIOs aligned with state-defined multicultural policies (Dahlstedt, 2003). However, critics like Schierup (1991) argue that this system led to the "ethnization" of migrant groups, transforming them into state clients rather than autonomous political actors. Although the 1968 Commission on Immigrants formally recognized rights to cultural preservation and transnational ties (Borevi, 2004), these rights operated within strictly defined governmental parameters.

By the 2000s, Sweden shifted toward a more integration-focused model, requiring SIOs to demonstrate how they contributed to migrants' societal participation. Yet, after the dissolution of the national integration agency (*Integrationsverket*) in 2007, responsibility for funding SIOs shifted to the Swedish Agency for Youth and Civil Society (*Myndigheten för ungdoms- och civilsamhällesfrågor*, MUCF). The current ordinance (2008:63) no longer mandates explicit integration activities but still emphasizes democratic governance and cultural preservation (MUCF, 2018). Despite these changes, SIOs remain constrained by structural dependencies on state funding, limiting their ability to act as independent advocates (Scaramuzzino, 2013). However, as Hellström (2017) observes, this framework maintained fundamental tensions between state control and organizational autonomy that continue to characterize Swedish immigrant civil society.

The contemporary system maintains specific eligibility criteria, including minimum membership thresholds and ethnic composition requirements, while providing annual funding averaging 300,000 SEK per organization (Frödin et al., 2021). Despite these structural supports, research indicates significant limitations in organizational capacities, with only 15% of national associations engaging in transnational development projects (Frödin et al., 2021) - a striking contrast to policy rhetoric framing migrants as key "development agents" in Sweden's international cooperation strategy (Government of Sweden, 2016).

For this study, we focused on two diasporas (Turkish and Iraqi) in Sweden, which offer a compelling lens through which to examine the complex interplay between migration, return aspirations, and state policies. These communities are not monolithic; they encompass multiple waves of migration (old settled, newcomers etc.), diverse ethnic and religious identities, and competing political agendas.

According to the Swedish Statistics (SCB, 2025), 57,389 people in Sweden were born in Turkey. Nevertheless, the number of *Turkish migrants* (migrants originating from Turkey) living in Sweden is much higher (Baser & Levin, 2017) – as most of them are already naturalised, 2nd generation migrants are not included in this figure ¹¹ The Turkish diaspora in

¹¹ Please note that this number does cover minority groups originating from Turkey. According to the data provided by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Turkish Republic (2025), approximately 150,000 Turkish migrants are living in Sweden

Sweden arrived in distinct waves: labour migrants (1960s–70s), political refugees (1980s–90s), and recent skilled migrants (2000s–present). Each wave carries different return aspirations—early labour migrants often envisioned temporary stays, while later refugees and professionals have more ambiguous or oppositional stances toward return.

The terminological complexity of “Turkish diaspora” itself reflects political tensions, as many minority groups from Turkey reject this label due to its nationalist connotations. The organizational landscape reflects these divisions, with pro-government Turkish associations coexisting uneasily with Kurdish rights organizations and Alevi cultural groups (Alinia et al. 2014; Baser, 2015). This fragmentation significantly shapes these communities' responses to Swedish return policies, creating a spectrum of engagement from cautious cooperation to outright opposition.

The Iraqi diaspora represents Sweden's second-largest non-European immigrant community after Syrians, comprising 143,160 Iraqi-born residents and an additional 91,119 Swedish-born individuals with at least one Iraqi-born parent (SCB, 2025). This population has formed through successive waves of conflict-induced migration. The initial wave (1980s–90s) included Kurds, Assyrians, and Arab Muslims fleeing Saddam Hussein's repression during the Al-Anfal campaign and the Iran-Iraq War. A subsequent, larger wave arrived following the 2003 Iraq War, with particularly significant numbers of religious minorities - including Christians, Mandaeans, and Yazidis - seeking refuge in Sweden. These migration patterns have created a diaspora community deeply marked by Iraq's complex ethnic and religious divisions.

Like their Turkish counterparts, Iraqi diaspora organizations reflect internal divisions. Kurdish groups focus on political advocacy, while Assyrian organizations emphasize cultural and religious preservation. These groups' attitudes toward return are shaped by ongoing instability in Iraq, with some groups (e.g., Assyrians) viewing Sweden as a permanent haven, while others (e.g., Kurdish nationalists) maintain active return agendas tied to political mobilization¹² (Alinia et al., 2014). Iraqi organizations are similarly split: Kurdish groups lobby for autonomous Kurdistan, Assyrians prioritize cultural preservation in exile, and Shia/Sunni factions reflect Iraq's sectarian politics. These divisions influence their engagement with Swedish and homeland return policies.

Our research reveals a significant disconnect between Swedish return policies and diaspora organizations' priorities. Interviews with organizational representatives demonstrate that return - whether voluntary or involuntary - ranks low on their agendas. Most lack formal policies on return, reflecting both the complexity of the issue and their limited engagement with return-related projects.

These organizations adopt a cautious stance, expressing conditional support for voluntary returns, with the understanding that such decisions must be made in accordance with the individuals' free will and the availability of adequate support in the country of origin. As one representative articulated, *“If repatriation is to be encouraged, it must be in a way to meet the needs of those people... No one can be sent back empty-handed”* (MigS-2). This conditional support reflects a blended approach between a rights-based approach and a utilitarian one. However, as mentioned above, many organizations remain sceptical about “voluntary” return programs due to perceived myths surrounding financial incentives and

¹² We need to emphasize that these are not *fixed* positions. During the booming period of Kurdistan Regional Government, returning homeland became a dominant discursive pattern. However, worsening conditions in Iraq and Iraqi Kurdistan led many to re-consider their earlier plans.

reintegration support. The common belief is that after one has returned, “*governments do nothing!*”

Some informants are strongly opposed to forced returns, viewing them as a violation of human rights. A representative noted, “*Repatriation means only one thing, it means trampling on and violating all human rights... It is not acceptable to send people back to a war zone*” (MigS-3). This opposition is rooted in the belief that forced returns do not address the root causes of migration and often leave returnees in precarious situations.

The majority of migrant organizations that were interviewed do not have a clearly defined organizational policy on returns, which reflects their limited engagement with return-related activities. Returns are not a priority area for these organizations, which instead focus on integration, cultural preservation, and advocacy. This absence of policy underscores the disconnect between government directives and the realities of migrant organizations' operations, as many view return policies as detached from their core mission of supporting migrants in host countries, leading to indifference or disinterest.

Moreover, engagement with return policies poses significant reputational risks for migrant organizations. We designate this phenomenon as an “ontological mismatch”, which arises because involvement in return-related activities contradicts the foundational principles of many organizations, which prioritize integration and protection. Furthermore, return -even when designated as “voluntary”- is often equated with deportation and exclusionary practices, creating reputational concerns. As one respondent noted when asked whether his organization has ever been involved in projects that are related to return: “*...No, no, no. It would probably reduce our credibility a bit, I think*” (MigS-1).

Similar concerns are also mentioned by other migrant stakeholders, underlying ethical dilemmas of engaging in return related activities. One organization articulated this sentiment clearly: “*I think it would reduce our trust capital quite a lot among those we meet if we were to start talking about [returns] as well.*” (MigS-4). This statement underscores the ontological mismatch between the missions of migrant organizations --centred on integration, advocacy, and empowerment-- and government expectations for facilitating returns.

To sum up, migrant stakeholders demonstrate profound resistance and a reserved positioning to both forced and voluntary return policies, viewing them as ethically untenable or practically unfeasible given the conditions in many countries of origin. However, our analysis reveals nuanced exceptions - in specific cases such as supporting deportations of convicted criminals, we observed instances of discursive alignment or affinity among some migrant stakeholders. That said, the predominant stance remained one of deliberate disengagement from return discourse altogether.

The discrepancy between government projections and the actual experiences of migrant organizations is evident in several aspects. *Firstly*, while the government places a premium on immediate solutions, such as increasing the number of returns, it neglects to implement long-term strategies that address the fundamental causes of migration. In contrast, both migrant organizations and CSOs lack such an “agenda”. Instead, they place significant emphasis on voluntariness, human rights, and sustainable reintegration. This discrepancy is indicative of a more profound discord between the objectives of policy and the tangible realities of migration. *Secondly*, constraints in resources impede the capacity of diaspora organizations to engage meaningfully and influentially in activities related to returns. As highlighted by our respondents, these organizations lack familiarity with the complexities of current return

politics and legal frameworks, as well as the human capital necessary for engagement in such endeavours. This situation is recognized by state actors, and it cannot be rectified through short-term project funding. This scepticism among migrant organizations is a salient factor hindering their engagement in return-related activities. *Thirdly*, the ambiguity surrounding the policy's scope has led to uncertainty among stakeholders tasked with its implementation, resulting in a state of perplexity and disorientation.

4.2. Germany: Migration and Development Nexus, Diaspora Engagement, and Returns

Germany has developed a comprehensive approach to the migration-development nexus, articulated in its 2016 “Strategy for Migration and Development” (GFFO, 2016, p. 3). The strategy outlines four main objectives for inter-ministerial policy making in the field of migration and development¹³: 1) reducing the root causes of displacement and irregular migration; 2) enhancing protection for refugees in host countries; 3) leveraging regular migration, and 4) facilitating the return and reintegration of individuals without prospects to remain in Germany. While the strategy emphasizes a whole-of-government approach (GFFO, 2016, p. 3) - integrating foreign, development, and economic policies - it notably omits explicit references to diaspora engagement, despite Germany’s subsequent institutionalization of diaspora partnerships in its development cooperation framework.

The primary actors designing and implementing Germany’s development cooperation are the Federal Ministry of Economic Development and International Cooperation (BMZ) and the *Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit* (GIZ). The GIZ advises “*BMZ units on migration issues (G20 unit for policy issues) and also operates on the implementation side of programs, both global and sector-based*” (Interview P.Ad_G-1, 10.4.2025). As mentioned by policy advisors working for the GIZ migration programs, including diaspora, “*there are displacement, human mobility, and labour migration programs present at different times, in different phases, with different focuses, and across a large geographical span. These are called global programs, but there are also many other programs within GIZ that are more related to certain regions and run by the geographical divisions within GIZ and BMZ*” (Interview P.Ad_G-1, 10.04.2025). Both in advisory and implementation work, there is a common understanding that “*diaspora cooperation is important to development*” and “*diaspora is quite relevant for ensuring participatory processes*” (Interview P.Ad_G-1, 10.04.2025).

Return and reintegration (including that of irregular migrants) have gradually become part of Germany’s development cooperation/migration/diaspora policy agenda. Initial efforts in the 1980s supported migrant communities (diasporas) in Germany, but explicit linkages between migration and development through diaspora support emerged only after 2006.¹⁴ The 2007

¹³ The Strategy is the result of an interministerial consultation process between German Federal Office (GFFO), Ministry of Economic Development and International Cooperation (BMZ) and Ministry of Interior (BMI). It has been elaborated in a sub-Working Group on Migration and Development (EMN, 2005)

¹⁴ After initial attention to diaspora communities because of returning labour objectives and remittance flows, the passing of the Immigration Law in 2005 (broad-based recognition of ‘Germany as an immigration country’) and the subsequent National Action Plan for Integration (2006) raised additional awareness for migrant (self-)organisations and their potential for facilitating increasing

pilot programme “Promoting Migrant Organisations’ Commitment to Development Policy” sought to harness the diaspora’s potential, but MO/DOs were not yet considered strategic partners of development cooperation. That only started from 2015 onwards. Further initial projects around the 2010s and initiatives involving diaspora actors (entrepreneurs, MO/DO welfare organisations, etc.) included the instrument of mobility partnerships (e.g., with Moldova), the Promotion of Development Activities of MOs (from 2011), the collaboration of GIZ (then GTZ) and the *Zentralstelle für Auslandsvermittlung* (ZAV) of the Federal Employment Agency with counterparts in countries of origin (from 2013 onwards) and the “Returning skilled labour” project, that ran as “Returning Specialists” development programme starting in 2014 within the GIZ Programme Migration and Development (PME) that had been established in 2012. Geographically, the main focus of these initial support programmes was on Sub-Saharan Africa. While early programmes to support skilled workers to countries of origin aimed to relieve the pressure of the labour market in Germany, this focus gradually shifted because the Federal Employment Agency was aiming to recruit rather than return qualified workers because they were needed in the German labour market (Interview P.Ad_G-2, 03.04.2025).

A significant restructuring occurred in 2017 when the PME split into two streams: one focused on displacement and return (PME) and another on diaspora engagement (PMD, Programme Migration and Diaspora). It continued supporting returning experts, diaspora entrepreneurs and small-scale project funding in countries of origin. The name of the program and some features (such as duration, criteria etc) officially changed in 2019, becoming the PMD and *Fachkräftefonds Migration & Diaspora* (FMD) and they received relatively high funding and were enabled to act flexibly t.¹⁵

PME newly focused on displacement and migration, including a module on “informed return and reintegration” in the framework of the *Perspektive Heimat* project (“Returning to New Opportunities”) from 2017 onwards. Until today, this PME component is positioned at the interface of the Ministry of Interior with its Federal Agency for Migration and Refugees (BAMF) and the BMZ/ GIZ and aims to facilitate the reintegration of migrants and refugees from Germany in countries of origin. This manifested in the legislative period 2017-21 in a programmatic focus on the establishment of *migration advice centres* in migrants’ origin countries from 2018 onwards but included also the return and reintegration counselling (instrument of Reintegration Scouts) run by GIZ in Germany. Between 2017 and 2020, BMZ funded GIZ’s activities (both components) in the field of return and reintegration with 150 million EUR. The subsequent government, transitioning from Conservatives and Social Democrats to a coalition of the Green Party and Social Democrats for the term 2021-25, in its claim of a paradigm shift for migration policy, adjusted the 10 centres¹⁶ under the new name

levels of participation and integration in German society among relevant German authorities (at federal, state and municipal level) (SVR, 2019).

¹⁵ PMD: 07/2019 - 06/2023 FMD: 04/2019 - 03/2025 PMD: 95 Mio. Euro FMD: 37 Mio. Euro. 2022 Flyer. <https://www.giz.de/en/downloads/giz2022-de-programme-migration-and-diaspora.pdf>.

¹⁶ Established until 2022: Kosovo (2015), Albania, Serbia (2016), Tunisia, Morocco, Ghana, Senegal (2017), Afghanistan (2018-21), Iraq (2018), Egypt, Pakistan. Many of these centres were run in close collaboration or entirely by IOM, implemented via GIZ with BMZ funding. The centres in Egypt, Ghana, Morocco and Pakistan are co-funded by the European Union, while the services in Iraq are co-funded by the Switzerland’s State Secretariat for Migration (SEM).

*Centres for Migration and Development (ZME)*¹⁷, speaking of a lighthouse initiative in 2022 and a 360 degree approach given the attention to abandon the support for just unidirectional migration (from Germany to countries of origin) and to promote advice on regular pathways and labour mobility to Germany and the EU instead. In 2023, GIZ opened additional Centres in Jordan and Indonesia. The national implementing partners in the cooperating countries are the line ministries (e.g. ministries of labour, social affairs or migration) and subordinate authorities (e.g. employment agencies). The duration of the current project cycle is from 2023 to 2027.¹⁸ These centres are established outside of Germany to “act as advisory centres for people wishing to migrate to Germany, Europe or within their region via regular channels so as to work or continue their education outside of their country. The centres also advise people who have returned from Germany, Europe or other countries and need support with reintegration locally” (GIZ 2025, p.1).¹⁹ Within the new GIZ programming cycle 2019-22, one part of PME evolved into MEG (Shaping Development-oriented Migration) with a concerted focus on policy advice and support for partner countries “in leveraging the benefits of regular migration and engaging diaspora for sustainable development” on the one hand, and an operational dimension implementing hands-on collaborative projects on the other (GIZ/MEG, 2024).

German development cooperation policy and actors has increasingly institutionalized diaspora engagement, with migrant organizations now recognized as strategic partners by both BMZ and other key ministries (BMI) over the past decade. MO/DOs are formally recognised as part of an active civil society in development programming. While BMZ addresses migration holistically, including return policies, BMI and BAMF have primarily focused on strengthening diasporas’ organizational capacity to enhance integration outcomes in Germany. This participatory approach reflects a broader policy commitment to include diaspora communities as key stakeholders in development initiatives. As emphasized in the Diaspora Summit position paper (Adhikari et al. 2024), German authorities view diaspora groups as crucial partners in building inclusive, cosmopolitan, and sustainable society addressing global challenges. To this end, German authorities invite some diaspora organizations which are eager to cooperate during the consultation stages, advisory roles in policy implementation²⁰ and implementation of projects by offering the provision of funding and capacity-building support for development projects in their countries of origin.

The Programme Migration and Diaspora, mentioned above, exemplifies this approach, channelling support to education, healthcare, and entrepreneurship initiatives (GIZ, 2022). Complementary efforts like BMZ’s Migration for Development program (BMZ, 2019) promote productive diaspora investment seeking to move beyond consumption-oriented remittance

¹⁷ See <https://www.giz.de/en/worldwide/131161.html>. Accessed 10-04-2025- [Promoting fair labour migration and reintegration after return - giz.de](#).

¹⁸ <https://www.giz.de/en/worldwide/131161.html>. Accessed 10-04-2025- [Promoting fair labour migration and reintegration after return - giz.de](#).

¹⁹ GIZ 2025. Promoting fair labour migration and reintegration after return (2025_ZME-website_en_Promoting fair labour migration and reintegration after return - giz.de, p. 1). Last updated December 2025

²⁰ In 2024, the GIZ established the Diaspora Advisory Board to advise the programme “Shaping development-oriented migration” (MEG) on its support for the diaspora. The board is made up of 16 highly qualified members of the diaspora from 14 countries of origin. The members of the board work on a voluntary basis and advise the MEG on its services for the diaspora. They offer advice not only on the concrete offers of the programme, but also on a strategic level, to improve the services offered by the MEG. Cf. <https://diaspora2030.de/en/participation>.

use toward development-impactful economic participation. As one policy advisor noted, implementation effectiveness remains contingent on partner country receptiveness to such diaspora engagement models (Interview P.Ad G-1, 10.04.2025).

There is a clear commitment of German development cooperation (DC) policy to the Agenda 2030 of the United Nations. Under the name Diaspora2030, they aim to show the significant contribution that the diaspora can make towards achieving these goals. It supports individuals and organisations from the diaspora in Germany, helping them leverage their skills and expertise in the best possible way. The policy advisors highlighted that

“We see diaspora also as one cross-cutting issue it's not only the diaspora cooperation, right, it's a role for diaspora in labour migration for example, we have just started an exchange also about diaspora in fragility with our technical department where we see special trends on countries maybe when we look at Syria or Ukraine, for example.” (Interview P.Ad_G-1, 10.04.2025).

For the longest-existing development cooperation instrument, the Returning Experts – now Returning Expert Fund/ Fachkräftefonds Migration & Diaspora (FMD) under PMD – strong relations exist given the long-term cooperation and communications with up to 22 countries worldwide and subsequent implementation experiences that could now be used in the context of return migration to Syria and Ukraine. As the policy advisor explained, there is a belief for the benefit of this program for the origin country. (Interview P.Ad_G-2, 03.04.2025.)

4.2.1. German Government’s Approach to diaspora organizations, development cooperation and return

German development cooperation has increasingly formalized diaspora engagement through various programs and participatory mechanisms, though this relationship remains marked by structural imbalances and operational challenges. The approach reflects both genuine efforts at inclusion and utilitarian tendencies in policy implementation. In the words of a policy advisor, *“We are trying to achieve the inclusion of diaspora in the participatory processes in the BMZ and strengthen diaspora engagement”* (Interview P.Ad_G-1, 10.04.2025). This seems to suggest that diaspora organizations are used by the Ministry for the sake of displaying its participatory approach and that performativity is weighted more than diaspora development and benefits. Interviewees reported that they often feel used by authorities when they invite them: *“Whenever it fits, they [BAMF] invite us, but they want to do the talking and do not listen”* (Diaspora org representative, 25.04.25). And sometimes they are not invited, yet their idea for an initiative (e.g., for a federal level Afghan Diaspora Workshop) is adopted without crediting the diaspora members.

German authorities employ multiple channels to involve diaspora organizations (MOs/DOs). Examining the ‘instruments’ GIZ and BMZ employ to engage (‘invite’) the diaspora partly supports this observation, but also reveals differences. On an operational level, GIZ uses an email list²¹ of consented MO/DOs to disseminate and request information. *“It’s really not rocket science; we are asking and we are receiving.”* (Interview P.Ad_G-1, 10.04.2025). More

²¹ An answer to a written request of a German member of parliament MPs about the ‘Diaspora meets BMZ’-event in April 2021 revealed that the email list contained 946 entries in the same year. Although all those organisations had reportedly been invited to the event, only four attended, causing the MP to direct the written request to the BMZ for answer (Deutscher Bundestag, 2021, 19229).

notably, BMZ has facilitated diaspora participation in high-level forums, including inclusion in German delegations to the Global Forum on Migration and Development (GFMD 2020) and organizing dedicated events like “Diaspora meets BMZ” (2021) and regular Country Exchanges (*Ländergespräche*). These platforms provide MO/DOs visibility and advocacy opportunities, potentially leading to sustained funding (Interview P.Ad_G-1, 10.04.2025). Ambivalence surrounds the installation of gatekeepers, such as large international humanitarian organizations that order the field of MO/DOs on behalf of the GIZ.

Despite these engagement mechanisms, significant power asymmetries persist. The dependency of MOs/DOs on German funding bodies creates an uneven dynamic where organizations must navigate bureaucratic requirements that favour established, well-resourced groups. In the context of increasing funding and public budget cuts, larger, more established organizations are better positioned to sustain themselves as they are more likely to have the capacity to write new project proposals and successfully navigate the bureaucratic and administrative requirements of German authorities because they have the personnel and time resources. Smaller or newer initiatives frequently struggle with the administrative burdens of proposal writing and compliance, leading to irregular funding and marginalization (Diaspora Beyond 2024).

Undoubtedly, there is strong interest on both sides (BMZ/ GIZ vs. MS/DOs) to engage with each other. However, the power differential between the funding bodies and the receiving organisations cannot be denied as the latter depend on the former for sustenance and organized survival. This partly explains the ad hoc activity modus operandi of some MO/DOs that may receive short term project funding one or two times, albeit not in a consistent manner. Considering the highly diverse landscape of MO/DOs in Germany and political stakeholders' tendency to engage with established, preferably umbrella organisations, there is a risk of the structural marginalization of new and inexperienced MO/DOs that do not or cannot be part of a larger structure. The challenge of representation is significant and also causes tensions among MO/DOs whose members hail from the same country of origin. While the prospect of forming a common voice and joining forces for advocacy goals and funding proposals seems to support the integration of initiatives into larger representative bodies, such as diaspora umbrella organisations, the diversity of origin-country diaspora representations which are differently positioned and reveal cleavages and splits within and among the communities, speaks against it. Furthermore, authorities' power position as facilitators and funders can harm diaspora bodies (of whatever format). For example, internal divisions within a diaspora from a specific country can result in competition among different generations of diaspora members. In such cases, community needs may not be understood. Funding decisions that favour one organisation over another and preferential treatment of the same organisations over years may deepen existing cleavages. Importantly, prejudices among the staff working in different state agencies, which may reflect broader prejudiced and racist attitudes and structures in society, cause grievances. This is most pronounced in the preferential treatment of Ukrainians over Syrians and Afghans, and of Syrians over Afghans, especially Afghan women.

The MO/DOs' relations with German authorities (from ministries to local job centres), institutions and funding bodies (such as the Robert Bosch Foundation and Mercator Foundation) are manifold and take place at the municipal, city district, federal and state levels.

Consequently, the experiences of misunderstanding and misuse are manifold.²² Furthermore, it seems that German authorities have yet to realize that conflict diasporas have special needs and that migrants from a country with decades of violent conflict history face more comprehensive integration challenges compared to those from countries with shorter conflict histories. Thus, the invitation aspect is well-intentioned but poorly implemented thus far. In 2013, the BMI/ BAMF started a programme to provide structural support to MO/DOs to address their insufficient participation capacities. During the funding period from 2017 to 2021, following the influx of large migrant numbers in Germany, the support focussed on organisations engaged in reception and integration work, again demonstrating the politically driven selection of beneficiaries.

For the German authorities, identifying which diaspora organization to connect is challenging. The GIZ used to focus mainly on umbrella organizations, but realized this method was ineffective within a year: *“We have tried to identify more organizations that might be smaller or even individuals that are interested in information on participatory processes and do that mainly by an email list that we spread through our partners with diaspora organizations that they have been in touch with and we invited them to join this email list”* (Interview P.Ad_G-1, 10.04.2025). As another noted, *“The objective was always there to be more inclusive but um we couldn't figure out how and now we have tried to do it by this kind of email”* (Interview P.Ad_G-1, 10.04.2025). Besides the inadequacy of tools and working examples, the diversity within diasporas is a real challenge, as policy advisors acknowledged: *“diaspora is diverse and there's not one diaspora; not everybody is organized in an organization: not every organization is affiliated to an umbrella organization and so on and so forth. We didn't really manage in our daily work to reach out to this diverse diaspora”* (Interview P.Ad_G-1, 10.04.2025)

Another challenge is the limited interest of the diaspora in development cooperation and participatory processes (Interview P.Ad_G-1, 10.04.2025). Despite the policy focus and invitation from development cooperation actors, such as GIZ for diaspora organizations, structural challenges impede equal cooperation, effective participation in decision-making processes and funding applications. This is particularly difficult for *“small, young and purely voluntary associations, worsened by bureaucracy, making efforts unsustainable because preference is given mainly to short-term, one-off projects with no connection to previous measures”* (Diaspora Beyond 2024, p.1). In general, many diaspora organizations face challenges related to financial constraints, administrative complexities, and personal burdens, which hinder the sustainability of many initiatives.

When it comes to return, this desire for engagement is even less. According to one international humanitarian organization with a large diaspora engagement portfolio, *“Return programming is something we try not to touch, because it's the rhetoric in Europe around return is, is so bad, that we don't, we really fear being associated with promoting ret”* (Interview IHO_G-1, 05.09.2025). It is difficult to claim that there are well-established, effective partnerships between diaspora organizations and national authorities responsible for migration and return. While ad hoc, project-based collaborations exist in the realm of return and development cooperation, they have not matured into lasting partnerships. We only came

²² However, diversity does not only constitute a complication on the side of the German authorities but also migrant initiatives and organisations reported the difficulty of navigating the diversity of multi-level potential counterparts for advocacy work, policy advice/ political participation and funding matters.

across one organization in a previous project on reintegration that was invited to support a German return and reintegration program (counselling). The founder of this nationwide association for networking the West African diaspora said that

We established contacts, but cooperation is not yet taking place, as the current project is focusing first on preparation for return to Germany. Hopefully, this module can be integrated into the next phase of the project. We also get requests from reintegration scouts to see if we can support them on-site as well. ...we have also made the experience that it is important to focus on the job perspective when someone decides to return. This could be done in cooperation with the diaspora who went back or who are active on the ground. In our work with returnees, it's important to ask people who return what they want to do when they get back. Not everyone is suitable for self-employment. Cooperation with local entrepreneurs would be a great opportunity, that's the idea now. (Interview MigG-O1, 09.07.2021)

The organisation took a role in a project having a return & reintegration counselling funded by BAMF.

We have just had a case of counselling for a woman from Ghana who wants to return, but has already been here for 11 years and no longer has anyone in her home country. We say that we need a network there just as we do here, and that this network is willing to accompany returnees in their social reintegration. This network could also consist of former diaspora members, it could be a contact point or an association like us, nothing big. In each country it would be important to select ten NGOs or members of the diaspora and work with them, for a smooth transition (Interview MigG-O1, 09.07.2021).

4.2.2. Diaspora Migrant Organizations Approach to Returns in Germany

Germany has a complex and populous diaspora landscape, which includes both registered organizations and various initiatives. Due to this heterogeneity, different diasporas are approached differently by development cooperation agencies and humanitarian actors, particularly during times of crisis or emergency, such as the Ukrainian, Syrian, Afghan crises.

Determining the precise number of migrant-diaspora organisations (MO/DOs) in Germany is challenging. Current estimates suggest between 12,400 to 14,300 active MOs, representing approximately 3% of Germany's non-profit sector (Adhikari et al., 2024). The majority incorporate legally as *eingetragene Vereine* (registered associations), though many maintain informal structures outside of official registries due to structural constraints and bureaucracy (Barglowski and Bonfert, 2022; Mualem, 2024). A review study on MO/DOs notes that:

The German political system has become considerably more open toward the organizations in recent years. The development of migrant organizations is embedded in a progressive social integration of their clientele. So, the importance of cross-border connections is reduced over time, and the national aspect is thus of remarkable importance for the development of the organisations (Halm and Sauer 2023, p. 49).

To improve the representation of MO/DOS, both the federal and state governments have financed the creation of federal associations for migrant organisations. Currently, there are 36 active associations (Mualem, 2024). Mualem (2024) identifies five types of federal associations. The first type, referred to as Diaspora associations (*Diasporaverbände*), advocates for the recognition of migration-related diversity and informs the public about the living conditions of particular migrant communities in Germany and globally. The second type, group associations (*Gruppenverbände*) aims to make empowerment the central theme

of its advocacy by focusing on the development of a migration society and establishing itself as specialists in anti-discrimination and equality matters. Third, specialised group associations (*Gruppenfachverbände*) focus on topics related to integration and equal participation (e.g. education or welfare) and serve as expert contacts for implementing target group-specific integration policies. Fourth, specialised umbrella associations (*Spitzenfachverbände*) strengthen practical integration work of MOs and support cross-community political demands to reduce central barriers in concrete integration areas. The fifth type, unity associations (*Einheitsverbände*), aims to raise public awareness of the post-migrant reality and promote cross-community political demands to strengthen equal participation opportunities across policy fields. Examples include a federal participation law or a law to promote democracy.

In our limited set of interviews, we encountered organisations that aligned with the first, fourth, and fifth categories. One organisation initiated its advocacy work against discrimination targeting African communities in Germany, later evolved into the fifth group, a unity association aimed at promoting the post-migrant experience. Another Turkish umbrella organization specialises in group associations, acting as a liaison for policymakers by highlighting cross-community and cross-sectoral policy needs. Afghan organisations generally align with specialized group associations that focus on integration issues, and to a certain extent, political advocacy. However, they generally do not explicitly oppose Germany's return or deportation policies, except for the existing umbrella organisation (Dachverband VAFO) and one that has emerged as an anti-deportation movement. It is noted that some organisations, which might not be classified as MO/DOs, are routinely identified as focusing on deportation issues. For example, *Neue Deutsche Organisationen* (New German Organisations) is running a campaign called “Nie wieder ist am 23. Februar” (Never again is on the 23rd of February) in response to the growing debate on “deportation” and “remigration” (NDO 2025). ProAsyl is also known for providing legal support to migrants at risk of deportation.

4.2.3. Afghans/Afghan Diaspora in Germany: invited for return and diaspora cooperation

By the end of 2024, 445,100 Afghans were registered in Germany's Central Foreigners Registry (Ausländerzentralregister, AZR). Other sources mention higher numbers, with Mediendienst Migration (2025) estimating roughly 476,000. Interviewees with an Afghan migration background claimed that about half a million Afghans currently reside in Germany. This marks a minimum six-fold increase since 2014, when the Afghan population in Germany had reached its previous peak of 75,385. Due to the insecurity in Afghanistan prior to 2021, the Taliban's takeover in August 2021, and subsequent growing humanitarian challenges, the number of asylum seekers from Afghanistan spiked and remains high.²³ The latest statistics show that 252,000 Afghans had received a protection status in Germany by 31 December

²³ For an overview of a) how asylum seekers' figures developed since 2021, see Mediendienst Migration (2025), <https://mediendienst-integration.de/migration/flucht-asyl/afghanische-fluechtlinge.html>, and b) for entries and exits of Afghans to and from Germany over the last five years (2020-2024), see the published numbers by the German statistics authority: [https://www.destatis.de/DE/Themen/Gesellschaft-Umwelt/Bevoelkerung/Wanderungen/Tabellen/wanderungen-nach-staatsangehoerigkeiten-jahr-03.html?view=main\[Print\]](https://www.destatis.de/DE/Themen/Gesellschaft-Umwelt/Bevoelkerung/Wanderungen/Tabellen/wanderungen-nach-staatsangehoerigkeiten-jahr-03.html?view=main[Print]) Accordingly, the net immigration per year increased from 2020 (8,357; 2021: 33,621) peaking in 2021 – the year after the Taliban regained power in Afghanistan – with 60,837 and decreased in the following years 48,453 in 2023 and 31,014 in 2024.

2023. The influx of hundreds of thousands of Afghans to Germany in a few years has fundamentally changed the landscape of the Afghan diaspora in Germany (Pohl, 2022, p. 33) argues that the Afghans have become more politically active and mobilised due to increased engagement with new arrivals and anti-deportation protests, both of which are facilitated by social media. However, as of today, this research found that the political positioning of Afghans - in Germany has recently decreased considerably – for a variety of reasons (see below).

Spectrum of organized Afghan groups

What remains undebated, is the evolution of dozens, if not hundreds, of new Afghan immigrant associations (registered and unregistered) that have formed around different causes and objectives. These associations have varying geographical reach from town associations, to regional and national networks. Professional sources estimate that there are around 160 to 200 registered Afghan organisations. “*With informal networks, there are a lot more. Probably in every town*” (Interview, 15 April 2025). Additionally, a growing number of platforms have emerged as social media-only exchange platforms, existing, e.g., as Facebook or Instagram pages. Yet, the degree of activity varies, some were formed with great energy, registered and then became completely inactive. As one informed interviewee stressed, “*There are 160 organisations, but this does not mean that they are all active. Many are only registered but have no activities. I would estimate the number of active associations much lower*” (Interview, 25 April 2025). The dynamic and often adhocist activity patterns of Afghan associations are related to different factors. They are usually formed by one or two highly engaged individuals around their peer group, whether family-based, profession-based, ethnic or other. The nature of initiation sets a trajectory that shapes the organisation’s sustainability, target groups, and geographical reach. For example, academic associations within and going beyond Germany have been formed with ambitions to influence German and European policymaking regarding Afghanistan or to do research and build the scholarly capacities of their fellow Afghans. Afghan arrivals since 2014 have changed the existing landscape, primarily by prompting established organizations to support new arrivals and subsequent integration assistance. However, many new associations formed around these objectives as well. Notably, reintegration assistance has evolved from providing shelter and language training to offering comprehensive political education. With the political mobilization against the regime change in Afghanistan from 2021 onwards, there was a politicization to defend women’s rights and sensitize the public of “gender apartheid” in the country of origin. Thus, the spectrum of activities grew considerably broader if the ‘established’ organisations of the 1980s, 1990s and 2000s are compared to those that formed after 2014. In addition, the increasing variety and number of Afghan organisations in Germany that portray themselves explicitly as diaspora members (and partly representatives) indicates that the term “Afghan diaspora” has gained prominence and is used as self-designation (Pool, 2021; SVR interview 25 April 2025). At the same time, the existing fragmentation among Afghans in Germany has likely contributed to these groups’ common understanding that the diaspora is highly diverse and heterogeneous. The existing Afghan umbrella organisation, VAFO, thus explicitly states in its vision that it aims to inform people about the diversity of the Afghan diaspora (VAFO 2025; interview, 5 May 2025).

Activism and political mobilisation among and across Afghan diasporas

A marked politicization set in after Germany and the EU closed two return migration agreements with the Government of Afghanistan in 2016. These agreements provided the framework for deportations of Afghans from EU countries, particularly Germany. A Germany-wide campaign “Afghanistan not safe”²⁴, a network of federal, European and local human rights organisations started to mobilize critical parts of civil society in Germany which also drew in many Afghan individuals and associations.²⁵ A second cause of political mobilization emerged after the regime change in Afghanistan in 2021 and the new government’s increasing suppression of human rights, particularly women’s rights. Third, driven primarily by civil society organizations at federal and subnational level throughout Germany, protests arose against the non-processing of hundreds of cases involving Afghans who had worked for the German government and other German institutions (local staff, also known as *Ortskräfte*). Similarly, Germany’s responsibility to accept Afghans in prominent positions who collaborated closely with international organisations (human rights activists, journalists, etc.) was the focus of demonstrations demanding the execution of the *Bundesaufnahmeprogramm* (Federal reception programme) for Afghans.

However, it is important to note that these topics are not exclusively “Afghan” in the sense that Afghans are not primarily responsible for setting the agenda. In addition, a closer look at who got mobilized and engaged for which cause, provides a glimpse into the high fragmentation of what is often called “the community of Afghans” in Germany. At face value, “the Afghan diaspora” is strongly divided, and differences in positionalities of the different diasporas are especially evident in mobilization attempts around issues with implicit political messages, such as women’s rights, deportations, but even the Federal reception programme (BAP) and the ‘saving’ of the *Ortskräfte* who feel threatened by the new regime and cannot live anymore in Afghanistan. On the one hand, diasporas represent the entire political spectrum of Afghan politics, from Taliban sympathizers to fierce anti-Taliban voices. On the other hand, even concerning the humanitarian realm, Afghan interviewees have repeatedly said that there is not much cross-group mobilization and solidarity. For example, while the earthquake in Herat in 2023 activated considerable financial donations from across Europe and Germany, the main donations primarily came from those people in the different host context diasporas who have links to affected areas. Many Afghans in Germany are highly sceptical and dissatisfied with the special reception/ repatriation programmes for their co-nationals because they believe the programmes are highly selective, and the processes are questionable. They also feel that the programmes ignore the plight of the Afghan population enduring under Taliban rule or persecution in Pakistan and Iran. Thus, political mobilization for any of the causes discussed above has been rather limited due to high intra-communal fragmentation.

Interviewees attested that political positioning and engagement are even in strong decline. Given the shift in the political climate in Germany, many reported developing fears and anxiety, not least because they anticipate or experience hostility in Germany after several violent attacks by Afghanistan-origin persons in Germany in 2024 and 2025. A legal advisor

²⁴ <https://afghanistan.not-safe.de>

²⁵ The bigger and more consolidated associations that formed in the 2010s have evolved from being ‘Afghan’ organizations and centring narrowly around Afghan needs in the classical format of ‘Diaspora Associations’ (cf. the distinctions in the first part of this Digest above) to topical alliances and working with and for all kinds of clientele, thus as part of ‘normal’, i.e., non-diaspora-initiated civil society (organizations).

for Afghan clients reported that numerous Afghans with a residence permit fear to be deported soon; a psychosocial worker confirmed the same impression about people with residency permits and secure employment status (Interview, 31.03.2025). Of the 252,000 Afghans with protection status in Germany, only 20,630 have unlimited protection status, while the great majority, 231,365, have temporary stay permits that require annual renewal (Mediendienst Migration, 2025). For these, family reunion is allowed only in exceptional cases as of May 2025. The latest anti-migrant policies in Germany, including announcements of the new government coalition (whose term started in May 2025) to deport Afghans in the future, after a first deportation flight (allegedly with prosecuted criminals only) to Kabul had taken place still under the previous government coalition in August 2024, caused widespread fear among Afghans with non-permanent status that they will be deported. Others, who already obtained German citizenship, fear the revocation of citizenship and deportation (Interview, 25.04.2025). The general suspicion that populist politicians put Afghans under and how they use the attacks of individual perpetrators for stirring up anti-immigration/-immigrant sentiments has become unbearable for many. One interviewee shared that she is considering emigrating from Germany due to pervasive racism, and her desire for her son to grow up without feeling like a second-class citizen (Interview, 25.04.2025). Political rhetoric about deporting Afghans despite the unchanged situation on the ground in Afghanistan destroys the trust in the German political system. As a legal advisor dealing mainly with Afghan clients noted,

“So, if you think about Afghans in Germany in 2025, you should know that for six months, or a bit more perhaps, the situation of asylum seekers is deteriorating massively. Ten years ago, most of them didn't get any protection in Germany, or basically 50-50. And then at some point less than that. Then the Taliban came to power and it was completely different. For the last six months, roughly speaking, we have seen an extremely high number of rejected asylum applications. It's really very clear. Women get protection because of the whole lack of rights in Afghanistan. Families too. But men are no longer at all. Or extremely little. We see men with rejected asylum applications every day. And men with positive decisions have become significantly fewer. And that was an extremely big change compared to the end of last year. And that's a return to the situation of 2015, 2016, 2017. That's really blatant. It's really obvious that after Mannheim, the attack in Mannheim, the decision-making policy has suddenly changed. If I'm cynical, I would say this attacker in Mannheim has made Afghanistan safe. Because someone who applied for asylum a month earlier and someone who applied for asylum a month later have completely different fates and decisions. Although the situation in Afghanistan has not changed. And that will again lead to great uncertainty in Germany” (Interview with legal advisor, 23.04.2025).

Moreover, Afghans note that even the protection status/ deportation ban for Afghan women at the EU level (and valid in all member states) is also not enforced 100 per cent (Interview, 31.03.2025) – constituting another fissure in the previously built-up trust in the German system. Thus, the fear of making a mistake, e.g. forgetting an appointment, being filmed at a protest or generally, sticking one's head out too far - reportedly restrains Afghan respondents and other community members from activism and political engagement. Additionally, several interviewees spoke about feeling of powerlessness within the political system, *“Who are they to change anything regarding German migration policy and practices?”* (Interviews, 4 and 31.03. 2025), others expressed a lack of experience and knowledge on how to do this (Interview, 21 March 2025). Other reasons for remaining silent were the aforementioned lack of solidarity among Afghans, organisations' non-political stance (Interview, 4 March 2025) and the secrecy surrounding deportations, which would prevent intervention by agencies

(Interview, 31.03.2025). Many of the cohort who arrived after 15 August 2021 have Afghan passports that are expiring soon. Given the absence of diplomatic relations between Germany and Afghanistan, the only operational consulate of Afghanistan in Munich has to deal with all passport extensions and applications which takes disproportionately longer than before and puts Afghans at potential risk to lose their status because of invalid documents. What had been conceived as merely an administrative process given the deportation ban valid for Afghanistan, has increasingly become a matter of uncertainty and fear. This leads to negative coping practices in daily life, e.g. thinking about emigration, avoiding going out in public anymore unless necessary, and avoiding speaking Dari or Pasho in public. In other words, the level of perceived discrimination, paired with a perception of undeservingness and subsequent fear, and even shame as well as denial and avoidance (of identifying/ introducing oneself as Afghan, of using the term Afghanistan anywhere in public where others could hear it and instantly make a judgment, etc.), is very high.

Integration focus trumps transnational engagement and anti-deportation stances

This research reveals a striking paradox: despite facing persistent populist hostility, Afghan-origin communities in Germany rarely mobilize collective resistance. The key explanation lies in their overwhelming focus on immediate integration struggles—a daily battle for basic stability that leaves little room for political activism. To best secure a more permanent status in Germany, many reported that the challenges of employment (training, professionalization, dealing with the requirements of the employment agency), language improvement and making ends meet as families with social security, health issues and education of children were sufficiently demanding to use up all their mental and physical resources. Thus, a focus on integration currently dominates the interest and scope of activities of Afghans. Even transnational engagement to improve the humanitarian situation, or defend the rights of co-nationals in Afghanistan, is less prevalent than integration-oriented engagement. The threat of forced returns is a vague concern that causes anxiety and fear (Raab, 2025); however, it is not considered “*a pressing issue*” and is perceived as only affecting a small group of Afghans, specifically criminals (Interview, 31 March 2025). Protesting and getting involved for this group is not considered beneficial or necessary. In fact, this research found that many Afghans support the deportation of criminals because of the belief that if criminals from Afghanistan are deported, as one interviewee noted, this will allow them to stay and potentially clean themselves from the “*Afghan stain*”, namely, “*to save the reputation of Afghans who are not all criminals and perpetrators*” (Interview, 25 April 2025). Along these lines, those who distinguish between individual criminals and the Afghan refugee community align with the political deportation agenda. This reveals the degree of cleavages among Afghans in Germany. According to one interviewee, those who have been living in Germany longer and claim to be integrated better, are explicitly in favour of deportations (Interview, 25 April 2025). However, it is important to note that such positions are not articulated at institutional level by associations or other networks and groups.

VAFO – the Afghan umbrella organization – is one of the few outlets to take a critical position on returns. At the same time, they lobbied for the continuation of the federal repatriation programme (VAFO, 2023), and against misperceptions and discrimination or the false depiction of Afghans as criminals/ knife-attackers, and ‘social parasites’ – narratives that are spread by populist anti-migrant parties (VAFO, 2025). The 12 current members of VAFO occasionally collaborate for events that disseminate these positions. For example, on 5 March 2025, they participated in a press conference together with representatives of Syrian groups,

facilitated by the Integration Commissioner of the State of Berlin. Thus, the member organisations and the VAFO office position themselves; however, not all do so at the same time, nor do they claim to represent the entire 'Afghan diaspora'. Acting with allies – other civil society organisations – is a key strategy for proactively addressing issues rather than merely reacting to them. Most individual organisations are reactive due to a lack of resources and other priorities on their agendas.

4.2.4. Syrian Diaspora in Germany: Recently invited for return and diaspora cooperation

The Syrian community in Germany is made up of both long-established migrants and a significant influx of arrivals since 2011, particularly in 2015-16, making the numbers around one million. In 2024, Syrians remained the largest group seeking asylum in Germany, though the German government halted processing new Syrian asylum claims after the fall of the Assad regime in December (Bosen 2024). The Syrian community in Germany is diverse, including a range of socio-economic, ethnic, and political backgrounds (Tuzi 2025; Popp 2022). Some newly arrived Syrians (after 2012-16) engaged with both registered and unregistered organisations, while others participated in more informal settings like forums, networks, initiatives, and WhatsApp groups. A Syrian MOs/DOs) is generally understood (including here) as one that is established and led (or co-founded) by Syrians.

The number of Syrian MO/DOs are not concrete. A review study on *Syrian civil society initiatives and organizations² in Germany* (between December 2023 and October 2024) identified “a total of 227 initiatives, of which 39 had ceased operations. While only 12 initiatives were established before 2011, previous studies suggest the actual number might be closer to 30.” (Tuzi 2025, p.9) This discrepancy in numbers may be due to some initiatives being inactive or the research team’s inability to obtain registration information for certain entities.³ Another study identified 177 Syrian organization that is founded and led(cofounded) by Syrians between 1979 and 2021 (Ragap 2021), while 84 of associations and initiatives with an online presence. The common observation is that Syrian associations are present almost every federal state, while density is higher in Western Germany, because many Syrian refugees settle in urban areas and federal states with more job opportunities, such as North Rhine-Westphalia, Bavaria, and Baden-Württemberg (Bosen 2024).

The large number of Syrian civil society organizations can be attributed the size of community and some conjectural factors. One interviewed expert explained it as

this is started mainly after 2015 where the Syrian organizations were pushed out of Syria’s neighbouring regions and they start to establish here in Germany. There had been organizations which are somehow established by the older diaspora members, they were either born or arrived here before 2011 actually in the 80s and 90s or maybe before. Then, when the Syria uprising started. one of their way was like to support is to establish these organizations and benefit from the German system or like the European system because it's not super hard to create an NGO. The problem comes later with the bureaucracy. German or French bureaucracy it's quite nightmare but like generally it was easy to establish them here (ExpertG-2, 24.04.2025).

Another review study, consistent with our own observations and those of other experts, highlights that a dynamic Syrian civil society has emerged in Germany. This group is actively engaged in humanitarian aid, long-term development, healthcare, education, community building, and women’s empowerment, as well as fostering intercultural dialogue, showing

similarities with other diaspora groups with refugee background, such as the Iraqi diaspora in Germany (Candan 2017, p.1). Many Syrian organizations had *initially unified around the Syrian revolution, but also experienced fragmentation. Over the years, the focus shifted more towards the “supporting integration in Germany, fostering intercultural dialogue and promoting mutual understanding between Syrians and the wider German society.”* (Ragab, N. J. and Katbeh 2018). *However, the Syrian MOs/DO also suffer from structural challenges.* We were told that even umbrella organizations of Syrian diaspora are not able to cover the administrative costs and had to close their offices. Nevertheless, there are still traces of efforts to address the Syrian crisis, despite facing insecurity, political stagnation, limited resources, and bureaucratic hurdles. The fall of Assad in December 2024 opened a new stage for their possible engagement with development cooperation in and return to Syria which will be discussed after the short overview of their activities

Activities of Syrian diaspora in Germany and Challenges

Since 2011, Syrian diaspora political activism has emerged in Germany, marking a shift from previous decades when fear of repression stifled opposition abroad. Since 2015, Syrian diaspora initiatives have engaged more in civil society activities, humanitarian efforts, and political advocacy abroad, as one representative noted:

*“More Syrian integration and cultural organizations have been founded in recent years. These organizations aim to strengthen the community and sense of belonging among Syrians as well as to provide support and assistance in arrival and integration processes in Germany.”*⁵

The Syrian diaspora exhibits significant diversity in their visions for Syria’s future and their approaches to integration in Germany. One interviewee said that

“The Syrian diaspora is not a monolithic group. Their experiences vary widely depending on when they left Syria, where they settled, and what they’ve accomplished since. This diversity must be considered when discussing their role in return and reconstruction. (MigG-S1, 15.02.2025)”.

There are various areas of engagement within Syrian civil society (Ragab 2021). Based on our research, we have made slight modifications to these activity categories. Additionally, we note that numerous organizations engage in multiple areas. The *first* area of activities is the provision of short-term humanitarian aid in the form of food and other relief supplies, medical care, and cash transfers aimed at alleviating the suffering of the Syrian population. According to Syrians interviewed in Germany, it is common among Syrians to send cash to extended family members to meet their immediate needs. The *second* field primarily focuses on culture, aiming to promote and preserve Syrian identity, foster cultural exchange, and strengthen relations and exchanges between the host society and Syrians, as well as community building through cultural events. Cultural associations, religious associations, or sports associations can fit into this category. One interviewee said, *“Our community organization brings together Syrians, including Christians and Assyrians, to discuss the situation in Syria and foster a sense of belonging.”* (MigG-S1, 30.01.2025). The *third* field is integration, which seeks to support Syrians through education, legal counselling, and language courses. These organizations manifest as grassroots community initiatives. According to interviewees, integration-related activities gained more momentum in recent years. They are also evolving into specialized group initiatives, as one interviewee mentioned that their group focuses on supporting Syrian teachers in Germany, sharing educational experiences, and addressing

challenges in the education sector. Professional associations and initiatives such as teachers' forums, business associations and student associations fall under this category. The *fourth* category is human-rights focused activities. Many Syrian diaspora initiatives engage in activities aimed at documenting human rights violations related to the Syrian conflict, protecting the rights of victims, promoting justice through national, regional, and international legal instruments, and protecting and promoting the rights of (ethnic) minorities, women and other marginalized groups.

These four activity areas do not solely concentrate on return or development cooperation. However, some of them encompass multiple activity areas related to these issues. For instance, one interviewee is a member of the Syrian Immigrants Association in one city, which aims to promote dialogue and collaboration among Syrians in Germany while aiding in Syria's reconstruction efforts. The organisation also seeks to "provide legal consultations and advocacy for refugees and displaced individuals." (MigG-S3, 25.01.2025). Some MOs decided to focus either on integration in Germany or the situation in Syria, as one representative explained, identifying his organization as a diaspora organization:

After the 2014-15 refugee movement to Germany, we actually faced, let's say, a strategic problem or issue. We had to discuss whether ... we should become a diaspora organization, focusing on the problems and the interest of Syrians here in Germany, or work inside Syria. We decided, actually, for the latter, mainly because we didn't have enough finance resource to cover staff expenses in Germany (MigG-S4, 02.05.2025).

Return/Deportation/Reconstruction

When we asked Syrian MOs/DOs about their stance on returns or anti-deportation efforts in Germany, interviewees frequently mentioned some individual activists and advocacy organizations such as ProAsyl, which was established in the late 1980s by human right advocates (Pro Asyl 2025). A few Syrians got involved in there such as Tareq Alaows who has been active in various organizations for the rights of refugees for many years. At ProAsyl, he works as a refugee policy spokesperson and speaker for campaigns and networking ((Pro Asyl 2025). These individuals can be identified as community leaders, influencers, volunteers who engage in advocacy about Syrians' rights in Germany. They also mentioned some German lawmakers and politicians of Syrian descent, as well as journalists and YouTubers.

There is some support for the return of Syrians who involved in crime as mentioned in our interviews:

"European countries, countries who need a clear, critical decision to send the people back, I'm not expecting that Germany, or also other countries, would be able to send Syrians back. If they will do a real evaluation of the situation inside Syria, so the security situation, the political situation, and also the situation regarding the construction, this will not be possible for Germany, at least, under this condition. They are criminals, they have to be sent back, as they did in Afghanistan for, for some cases, but not sending thousands of Syrians from Germany to, to go back to Syria. This will not be possible under these conditions, and I'm not seeing, actually, any chance for real improvement inside Syria for the next few months, at least, till the end of this year" (MigG-S4, 02.05.2025).

Nevertheless, political discourse creates a fear within Syrian communities in Germany, especially among those with subsidiary protection permits. NGOs recommend that

“my advice is also, if you are not sure, and if you have this fear, and so, probably, you can go to ProAsyl, maybe to other organisations, but try also to pay, like, 100 euro, and go to one of the lawyers, (.) and, uh, get more information and understanding about the situation, and this is what, what, (.) the, uh, on personal level, we can advise, you know, we can do it for other people” (MigG-S4, 02.05.2025).

Inside Syrian MO/DOs, there are some initiatives focusing on development cooperation and civil society engagement inside Syria. Many focused on improving the living conditions of the population in Syria e.g., projects to support the education system, development and maintenance of the medical sector, and assistance in securing livelihoods (microfinance projects). These initiatives promote civil society engagement in Syria and host societies and strengthen the capacities of Syrian civil society actors through networking, human resource development, and other capacity-building programs, civil society research and development, reconstruction and rehabilitation (ExpertG-2, 24.04.2025). As part of the civil society dimension, some initiatives focus on amplifying women's voices (MigG-S5, 30-01-2025). For example, one interviewed Syrian woman has been an active member of the organization advocating for raising awareness about honour crimes and women's rights in Syria (MigG-S5, 30-01-2025). The high level of diversity within groups is typical but presents a challenge for policies that prioritise the return-development nexus, especially regarding the diaspora's potential role in Syria's reconstruction. As one interviewee stated, *“he biggest challenge is bringing Syrians together. Over the past 50 years, there's been a lack of trust and understanding among Syrians. If there were a way to unite us—whether through donations, projects, or official channels—it could make a huge difference”* (MigG-S6, 20.02.2025).

Regarding the collective anti-return position, many initiatives can be mentioned. The most prominent one is the transnational anti-return campaign which was launched in 2018 and went on for a couple of years. *Syrianotsafe* is a German-Syrian campaign aiming for an indefinite deportation ban. The campaign started in 2018 as reaction to the discussions that the war in Syria had ended and deportations would be safe ([Facebook](#)).²⁶ It was also used in respect to the lifting of the ban on deportations to Syria in December 2020 by the Conference of Ministers of the Interior in Weimar. In Germany, ProAsyl and Adopt a Revolution joined the campaign protesting against the end of the deportation ban. The hashtag #SyriaNotSafe has been used especially in relation to the above-mentioned campaign and organisation. It is especially used in the German context, e.g. by the VDSH, but also in relation to other countries' policies, like [Denmark](#) or Turkey. The hashtag was primarily used in 2020 and 2021. In Denmark the hashtag was used when in 2021 the Danish government decided to cancel residencies and issue deportation notices to 94 Syrian refugees. Online posts used the hashtag to express the critique and for the protest against this law (Facebook, n.d.). The hashtag was also used as a protest against forced deportations and against the violence in Turkey and northern Syria ([Facebook](#)). Rather than MO/DOs, individuals and social media platforms, especially Facebook, are crucial for Syrian diaspora engagement. This includes tracing an anti-deportation stance. In depth research on online platforms is necessary, but it is beyond the scope of this research digest.

²⁶ The website doesn't work, however they have been active on social media until 2023 (Instagram and Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/SyriaNotSafeCampaign>). Recently, they haven't been active on social media anymore.

5. Common Discursive Patterns among the MO/DOs on returns

This analysis examines how migrant and diaspora organizations (MO/DOs) in Germany and Sweden (dis-)engage with the politically charged issue of return and deportation. Grounded in interview data with MO/DO leaders, activists, and community representatives, our analysis reveals how these organizations navigate complex moral, political, and survival imperatives via *five distinct discursive patterns*²⁷ adopted by DOs.

Table 1: Discursive Patterns of Diaspora Organizations on Return Policies

Patterns	Key Themes
Disengagement	Ethical objections; resource limitations; avoidance of politicization; not focus area for DOs
Conditional Support	Return as development tool contingent on safety and reintegration
Pragmatic Acceptance	Voluntariness and procedural fairness as prerequisites
Alignment (Deportations of Criminals)	Protection of community reputation; distinction between "deserving/undeserving"
Opposition - Moral opposition - Direct opposition	Forced return as state violence; transnational solidarity

5.1. Disengagement

Many diaspora organisations consciously maintain no formal position on return migration, adopting what appears at surface level to be a neutral stance. MO/DOs we interviewed in Germany expect that deportations will continue, and they do not see a role for themselves because it is a legislative, juridical, and political process, and organisations are “small” and “non-political organisations.” When we asked about their involvement one interlocutor responded that “*sometimes they asked me, but I don't know. We are not in this situation. You can go to a lawyer*”. (MigG-A4, 04.03.2025).

Some informants attribute the nonengagement in the civil society to the belief that deportation is a non-issue or invisible to the broader migrant community:

The deportation of Afghans is a small stream that is just continuing, and happening, yet no one pays attention. They merely report that Germany has chartered this flight with hundreds of Afghans. Each of these deportations is not really public. The government itself

²⁷ Diaspora perspectives on return migration often emerge as hybrid narratives, blending host-country's influences with homeland concerns. This hybridization underscores how diasporas reinterpret return through dual lenses of integration and belonging, creating distinct discursive frameworks that challenge monolithic national narratives. The FAiR project's (2024) identification of five key diaspora discourses (universal humanitarianism, post-colonial critique, migration/development pragmatism, nativist securitization, and civic integration) resonates well with the spectrum of engagement stances, from outright opposition to conditional collaboration that we have developed in this GAPs research digest.

doesn't want too much attention at a policy level. Yes, they announced that they are working on the return policy or on deportation, but when it comes to the implementation of that plan, it all happens too quietly (MigG-A3, 31.03.2025).

This is not to an extent that can attract attention. Okay. Or it is not mobilised with other organisations, probably something, but not a huge one. (...) (MigG-A1, 21.03.2025)

This disengagement, however, can be also considered as an active strategy shaped by multiple pragmatic considerations rather than mere indifference. Primarily focused on immediate integration needs such as language acquisition and employment support, these organizations allocate their limited resources toward services that benefit most constituents rather than contentious political debates surrounding deportation policies.

The absence of engagement with return issues frequently stems from structural constraints rather than ideological neutrality. Dependent on government and institutional funding tied to integration metrics, these organisations carefully avoid activities that might jeopardise their funding streams or draw scrutiny from authorities. One respondent said that *“which organisation in Germany usually does this? Caritas does it, AWO does it. We are not in this organisation. Because we do not have any agreement with IOM or BAMF.”* (MigG-02, 19.03.2025).

Some groups additionally harbour unspoken fears of state retaliation should they voice opposition to deportation policies, particularly those operating in contexts with shrinking civil society spaces. This cautious approach reflects an institutional survival strategy in an increasingly securitized migration landscape. One interview partner said that

To be honest, there is no serious discussion regarding deportation and even nothing about the people who were left behind. The focus has been more on how to influence this negative climate, which is shipping in Germany against Afghans. (MigG-A1, 21.03.25)

In practice, disengaged organizations maintain arm's-length distance from return-related matters unless directly approached by affected individuals. When confronted with deportation cases, they typically employ referral systems, redirecting community members to specialized NGOs better equipped to handle legal challenges or emergency support. This allows them to maintain basic solidarity while avoiding organizational risk. The stance is perhaps best captured in the tellingly brief statement: *“No, we don't have anything special about returns.”* (MigS-5). This seemingly offhand remark reveals much about the careful navigation of dangerous waters - acknowledging the issue's existence while firmly declining organizational involvement. The most common doing of MO/DOs is to refer the person-at-risk to a lawyer, *“we are trying to serve them. From the case of repatriation to the case of Duldung, we are busy with lawyers”* (MigG-02, 19.03.2025).

One umbrella organisation for the African community also expressed similar views about acceptance and its limitations, yet still offers individual solidarity, as mentioned by the Turkish and Afghan umbrella organisations we interviewed.

When we hear about deportation, it's often acquaintances or people we know from our circle. We try to get lawyers involved who can then intervene, because as a civil society you can do that, you hardly have any leverage, you don't even have the right to visit under certain circumstances. That means, so to speak, here too we are trying, so to speak, through female lawyers, who in turn also work with the refugee organisations or themselves. That we then, of course, also provide support on a small scale, for example, so that people can

take the train somewhere, or to visit people in custody pending deportation somehow. But it's usually the case that it is usually also very close to the point where deportation happens, or so, that it is almost a bit late or so. (MigG-03, 06.03.2025)

The pattern reveals a fundamental tension in diaspora organizational behaviour. While prioritizing integration work aligns with both community-needs and funding requirements, it creates gaps in support for those facing deportation. This strategic silence can be read as both a form of quiet resistance—a refusal to legitimize forced return frameworks—and a pragmatic concession to political realities. The approach allows organizations to continue their core mission of supporting settled community members, even as it risks leaving the most vulnerable without institutional advocates. Ultimately, this disengagement underscores how structural pressures shape the boundaries of diaspora activism, forcing difficult choices between comprehensive engagement and organizational survival.

5.2. Conditional Support for returns with emphasis on reintegration

Diaspora organizations adopting a position of conditional support for returns navigate a complex middle ground, balancing pragmatic engagement with moral reservations. Their discourse centres on the idea that return migration can only be justified under specific circumstances -namely, when safety, security and economic opportunity in the origin country exist. This perspective often frames return as a future possibility rather than an immediate expectation, emphasizing that improved conditions in origin countries must precede any large-scale repatriation efforts. All Syrian organizations interviewed in Germany highlight the “lacking of conducive conditions” to discuss returns from European countries.

In practice, MO/DOs taking this position of conditional support tend to avoid direct involvement in contesting return processes or facilitating them. Instead, they focus on advocacy, pushing for policies that ensure “safe and dignified” returns. Their activities frequently include participation in policy dialogues with host state governments and NGOs, where they emphasize the need for robust integration programs in the host country and reintegration conditions in the home country. By engaging with institutional actors, they aim to influence the design of asylum and integration policies in the host country directly, and returns indirectly, ensuring that migrants' rights and needs are prioritized.

The conditional nature of their support is encapsulated in statements such as, *“If repatriation is to be encouraged, it must meet the needs of those people... No one can be sent back empty-handed.”* (MigS-2). This quote underscores their insistence that return should not equate to abandonment, but rather to a structured process that addresses both the material and psychological well-being of returnees.

The leader of one DO in Germany, who was invited to be involved in return counselling by German authorities stated,

There are three steps in return: first, return preparation (which takes place here), the return journey itself, and then reintegration. All aspects need to be thoroughly planned, and from our experience, the people often have little time before their obligatory departure to participate in activities. Therefore, one must identify opportunities at the political level to grant them time to qualify. Return and reintegration should be viewed as a chain, and all key actors ought to collaborate in this context at the political level, exchanging ideas and developing coherent, unified projects. BMZ and BMI need to work together even more. If someone decides to return, we require programmes that support them for one-two years in both economic and social reintegration. There must be structures in place that can provide this support (MigG-O1, 09.07.2021).

Moreover, MO/DOs highlighted that some practical measures put in place for returns such as ensuring pension transfers for elderly returnees, providing trauma counselling services for those who have endured conflict or persecution, and demanding anti-corruption reforms in origin countries to guarantee returnees' safety and economic stability. Without these conditions, they argue, return risks replicating the very hardships migrants sought to escape.

One interviewed Syrian MO/DO in Germany, which is engaged in ongoing humanitarian projects within Syria, stated that *"You are sending the people back but not organising a process, lacking sufficient mechanisms or authority to address issues upon their return, such as reclaiming returnees' previous homes and their registration in bureaucracy.* (MigG-S4, 02.05.2025). In general, the discourses are not limited to pre-return stages and removal enforcement, rather focusing on which steps should be taken upon return in a way to align with the idea of sustainable return.

5.3. Pragmatic Acceptance with Criteria on Fairness of the Removal Decision and Voluntariness in the Process

Diaspora organizations adopting a pragmatic acceptance stance approach the issue of return migration with cautious openness, but only under strictly defined conditions regarding the decision process and voluntariness during return.

While these organisations recognise the potential in voluntary return programmes, they remain deeply sceptical about their implementation. They criticise such initiatives for being structurally coercive, arguing that migrants often face indirect pressure to accept return due to precarious legal status, limited integration prospects, or cuts to social support. This scepticism leads to careful, arms-length engagement with institutional actors. Rather than formal partnerships, these diaspora groups provide ad hoc support—such as legal referrals or temporary shelter—while avoiding institutionalised collaboration that might legitimise flawed return systems or jeopardise their priority work on integration.

One informant from an Afghan organisation implicitly referred to the problems in the asylum decision process and subsequent removal orders by mentioning the appeal process:

"The people who must be deported or they will leave Germany. But, well, from my experience in the last eight or ten years, for example, the Afghans who were rejected, (...) for example, in BAMF, when they appealed back to the court, more than 70% of them, they got positive decisions. Well, that means the decision which has been made in BAMF is not fair (Afghan org. 04.03.2025).

Another Afghan informant, who works as a social worker and translator for an NGO, indicated problematic issues with the deportation procedures:

"A couple of months ago, an Afghan girl, who has been living with her family in Germany she has been called by the Ausländerbehörde, and they asked her to come, and they, took her from there to deport her, so, it's happening, so quiet (MigG-A3, 31.03.2025)

One Turkish-origin informant from a community organisation in Cologne, Germany also explained in detail how a young Iraqi asylum seeker was issued a return order due to the *"small contradiction in the testimony they gave when they first came here and last testimony about the birth place"* (MigG-02, 19.03.2025). In that case, although all family members obtained refugee status, this young person was issued a return order. In such a situation, if migrant organisations are approached, they offer individual support in accompanying the person,

assisting with translation, or referring her/ him to a lawyer. The social worker explained how he helps the person:

What do we do in practice? In such cases, the immigration office is our contact. Now the legal remedy is closed. You know, the Iraqi guy is at the individual counselling stage, I would like to point out that individual destiny is given here, especially in the bureaucracy. Is there really a misunderstanding? And can you put this forward with all sincerity? And we also need an official to believe this. (MigG-02, 19.03.2025)

While the previous pattern links to the sustainability of returns by reminding of the necessary conditions for reintegration, this discourse about pragmatic acceptance aligns with the voluntariness and dignity aspect of returns.

5.4. Alignment - Support for Deportations of ‘Criminals’

A distinct segment of MO/DOs adopts a stance in favour of deporting community members convicted of criminal offenses, viewing such measures as necessary to protect the collective reputation of their diaspora group. This discourse emerges from a palpable anxiety that high-profile criminal cases involving co-ethnics may fuel negative stereotypes, potentially jeopardizing the broader community's social standing and integration prospects in the host society. The position reflects a strategic calculation – by supporting the removal of individuals deemed problematic, these organizations aim to demonstrate their community's commitment to law and order, while distancing themselves from elements perceived as undermining their hard-won social position.

One feature of this discourse is the emphasis on “deserving” and “undeserving” returnees. For instance, while vulnerable groups such as refugees or victims of trafficking are seen as needing protection from forced returns, those labelled as criminals or security threats are often excluded from such considerations. An interview partner from an Afghan organization said,

“A distinction should be made between individual criminals and the whole Afghan refugees and communities. So criminal is a criminal. If he or she has committed a crime then she should pass all the procedures of the jurisdictions and then they should be deported. In terms of criminals, we do not have any tolerance, whether they are Afghans, non-Afghans, Germans, non-Germans (MigG-A2, 25.04.2025).

This discourse also highlights that removal is a judicial decision and not an administrative or political issue, other organisations (like MO/DO) should not “*interfere and intervene*” ((MigG-A2, 25.04.2025), even “should not protest”, unlike in case of other political issues.

This selective approach allows diaspora organisations to partially align with state policies; nevertheless, there are some critical perspectives. The first concern for some interlocutors is whether those deemed as criminals “*are all criminals, or not, this will be revealed when a background check happens*” (MigG-A3, 31.03.2025). One Afghan MO/DO representative stated that “*I think this will continue. And all those people who make even a minor mistake will be considered as an offense and later on criminalized* (MigG-A1, 21.03.2025).”

The second concern is whether deportation actually serves as appropriate punishment. Some argue that returning criminals to relatively stable countries like Nigeria constitutes a legitimate consequence, while others question whether deporting offenders to active conflict zones like Afghanistan amounts to excessive punishment, given the dangers awaiting them

These debates reveal moral ambiguities even among supporters of such deportations, highlighting how security concerns intersect with ethical considerations.

In our fieldwork, we did not come across organizations holding this view at an organisational level, but it was rather revealed in individual statements. However, during our interviews with the representatives of these organisations, we observed such alignment in the discursive realm. A key aspect in such articulations involves emphasizing distinctions between ‘law-abiding’ majority and ‘criminal’ outliers, as encapsulated in the statement: *“If they are disturbing the peace... they should be rehabilitated first, if not, sent back.”* (MigS-4). This carefully worded position suggests a preference for rehabilitation while ultimately endorsing removal as a last resort, framing it as a matter of communal self-preservation rather than unconditional alignment with state policies.

The stance can also be interpreted as a pragmatic survival strategy adopted by established diaspora groups navigating the politics of belonging in their host countries. By supporting certain deportations, these organisations attempt to position their communities as responsible stakeholders rather than problematic populations, even as this approach risks internal divisions and accusations of abandoning vulnerable members. The delicate balancing act underscores the complex trade-offs MO/DOs face when caught between state pressure and community solidarity. Nevertheless, many maintain a moderately critical stance toward blanket deportation measures and the increasing pro-deportation discourse in the host countries’ politics.

5.5. Opposition to Forced Returns

A vocal contingent of migrant activists and informal networks mounts principled opposition to forced return policies, framing deportation as a fundamental violation of human rights and an act of state violence. This discourse presents an uncompromising critique of host countries’ immigration regimes, arguing that governments increasingly prioritize expulsion over meaningful integration, even for long-term residents who have built lives in their adopted communities.

The opposition movement draws particular attention to the dangers facing returnees in countries experiencing ongoing conflict or political instability, as evidenced by social media campaigns like #SyriaIsNotSafe that publicises the risks of repatriation to war-torn regions.

Unlike more institutionalized diaspora organizations, resistance to forced returns typically emerges through loose, organic networks of migrant activists, often individuals who have personally experienced or narrowly avoided deportation themselves (MigG-04, 28.03.2025). These grassroots formations operate outside traditional NGO structures, employing direct action tactics that include providing safe houses for those facing removal, organising legal support teams, and staging protests outside detention centres or mobilize them as one informant in Germany mentioned:

“We aim to encourage those in deportation prisons to seek legal interventions and to create political scandals when opportunities arise, while also empowering refugees to protest against deportation. We tell them that if someone is deported from your camp today, just know that you’re the next person. Therefore, we are now mobilising refugees towards self-organisation in the camp and self-determination. If one person is to be deported and four policemen arrive, and you are 200 in the camp, how can you allow such things to happen?”

There are ways to create blockades and similar actions. These are the strategies that are proving effective” (MigG-04, 28.03.2025).

On a few occasions, such organisations initiate platforms or align with broader coalitions advocating for asylum rights, lending their voices to campaigns that promote transparent and humane policies. One activist in Germany mentioned that

“We have now deportation alarm...but long before deportation alarm we were the ones announcing every deportation flight online, we were publishing information because from the deportation prisons I get contact to know that the next position is this and when we accompany the process we know the dates so we announce the deportation and make this public and then when there's a deportation flight we announce the deportation flight so a lot of people never knew that there were deportations every month” (MigG-04, 28.03.2025).

The activism sometimes transcends national borders, with coordinated campaigns targeting specific deportation flights to countries like Nigeria (MigG-04, 28.03.2025) and Afghanistan, where returnees may face persecution or extreme hardship upon arrival. A few also document *“what was happening so we can have practical proofs for our critics up here”* about the return procedures (MigG-04, 28.03.2025).

The moral foundation of this opposition is captured in stark terms by one activist's declaration: *“Repatriation means trampling on human rights... Forced return is state violence.”* (MigS-3). This framing positions deportation not as a legitimate policy tool but as an extension of state power over vulnerable populations. The movement challenges the very notion of “voluntary” return in contexts where migrants face destitution or detention as alternatives to deportation, arguing that such choices constitute coercion rather than genuine consent.

However, anti-deportation activism also depends on the conditions and resources of MO/DOs. For the case of Afghans, we were told that

“Before 2021, the focus was mainly on migrants’ rights and against deportation. Organizations conducted large demonstrations in Berlin, and also they issued press statements. Now the main topics are gender apartheid, women rights, inclusive government, ... So, deportation is, uh, not a huge topic, but racism, and also attack, and a violent attack, is one of the main topics that I have witnessed recently. (Afghan org.250415, Pos. 74)

As highlighted in the quote, MO/DOs strategically choose engagement tactics (action/silence) based on host/home-country politics and resource limits. Yet even on sensitive issues like forced returns, they assert agency through alliances and discursive framing.

5.6. A Spectrum²⁸ Approach to Discursive Positioning

To conceptualize these patterns and show their dynamic interplay, we propose a semi-circular spectrum (Figure 1, below). This model positions *alignment* and *opposition* as polar endpoints, representing maximal cooperation with and resistance to state return policies respectively, whereas *disengagement* occupies the neutral ‘in-between’ position, marking strategic non-participation, and *conditional support* and *pragmatic acceptance* bridge the

²⁸ This approach will be further elaborated in a journal article.

middle ground. On the left, we distinguished *moral* and *direct* opposition as the latter assumes a more activist approach.

Figure 1 - A spectrum of discursive patterns (Source: The Authors)

The spectrum model rejects binary interpretations of MO/DOs as either “co-opted” or “oppositional”. Instead, it captures how organizations *navigate* return politics through *strategic silence* (disengagement), *negotiated compliance* (conditional/pragmatic positions), or *moral confrontation* (opposition). This fluidity underscores to recognize DOs as *heterogeneous actors* whose engagement depends on contextual stakes, rather than assuming uniform “diaspora partnerships”.

6. Conclusion: A Spectrum of Discursive Negotiation

This research has thoroughly explored the intricate role of migrant and diaspora organizations (MO/DOs) in the governance of return migration in Germany and Sweden, highlighting a significant gap between policy goals and the viewpoints of those involved MO/DOs. Our analysis shows that state efforts to utilise MO/DOs as partners in encouraging “voluntary” returns are regularly hindered by structural contradictions, political limitations, and significant misalignments between governmental strategies and the priorities of the diasporas. The research uncovers a landscape where diaspora engagement ranges from *direct opposition* to *strategic disengagement*.

Our analysis reveals that diaspora organizations (MO/DOs) engage with return policies through five distinct but overlapping discursive patterns²⁹, reflecting strategic negotiations between moral principles, community interests, and institutional constraints. These patterns—disengagement, conditional support, pragmatic acceptance, alignment, and opposition—are not static categories but fluid positions that diaspora organizations in

²⁹ We deliberately chose to frame these as discursive patterns rather than fixed ideological positions precisely because of what we witnessed in Germany and Sweden.

Germany and Sweden may adopt contextually, challenging the homogenized assumptions that underpin current policy frameworks.

At the heart of these tensions lies a paradox of instrumentalization. While Germany and Sweden increasingly frame MO/DOs as "partners" in return migration governance, their policies often reduce these groups to mere tools for implementation rather than meaningful stakeholders. This instrumentalization manifests most clearly in what we term the "policy projection gap" - where governments overestimate MO/DOs' willingness to act as return intermediaries while underestimating how contested return agendas constrain organisational agency. As evidenced by our five-fold patterns of diaspora responses - ranging from *disengagement*, *conditional support*, *pragmatic acceptance*, *alignment*, and *opposition* - most organizations approach return policies with significant reservations, perceiving potential and expected governmental instrumentalization attempts in this field as breeding mistrust that limits effective collaboration.

The expected collaboration between state authorities and MO/DOs in the field of migration and return is further complicated by structural barriers that actively discourage meaningful engagement, including short-term funding cycles (evident in Germany's PMD program and Sweden's annual appropriation letters) and bureaucratic hurdles. When one Swedish respondent noted that participation in return practices "would reduce our credibility" (MigS-1), they highlighted how engagement risks erodes hard-won community trust - revealing disengagement not as passive resistance but as a rational adaptation to policy designs prioritizing state convenience over diaspora capacity-building. Contrary to policy assumptions that MO/DOs will naturally participate in return programs, we found an ontological mismatch between the imposed policy projection and MO/DOs' concerns about self-image and priorities. Most MO/DOs do not work specifically on "returns" and do not find themselves in any meaningful role compatible with their core missions of integration and protection.

These tensions become particularly visible when examining spaces of engagement through Miraftab's (2004) framework of invited versus invented spaces. The five-fold patterns of diaspora stances demonstrate how return policies remain contested terrain, with MO/DO involvement hinging on ethical considerations or pragmatic solidarity rather than state-aligned agendas. Even though they are invited, MO/DOs do not consider that there are meaningful partnership attempts due to the power asymmetries and instrumentalization in line with state authorities' goals. They do not perceive the process as empowering or being listened to. These dynamics reflect a broader trend where "invited spaces" prioritize performative inclusion over substantive collaboration, exacerbating the contradictions between rights-based development agendas and securitized migration controls evident in both countries.

Both Sweden and Germany exhibit obvious contradictions between their rights-based development agendas and securitized migration controls. Sweden's international development agency SIDA maintains a focus on "voluntary repatriation and rights-based approaches", while political discourse on migration emphasizes stricter returns. Germany's BMZ funds diaspora-led development projects but excludes MO/DOs from return policy design. These gaps reveal a fundamental tension: states seek diaspora cooperation without addressing their critiques of return regimes. The exclusion is particularly striking given the critical stance many MO/DOs hold toward return policies. The result is a governance

deficiency where top-down policy formulations are imposed without consultation with the very communities they aim to engage.

We also observed a profound mistrust toward the notion of ‘voluntariness’ in return policies, which we interpret as a disconnect between top-down policy frameworks and the lived realities of migrants. This disconnect is significant because it reveals how even hypothetical discussions of return policies can evoke feelings of exclusion and insecurity among migrants, including long-settled individuals who hold host-country citizenship. For many, the mere mention of returns signals that their presence in the host country is contingent upon shifting political discourses, placing them in a perpetual state of trial and temporality. This fosters a sense of uncertainty and fear about their future, underscoring the emotional and psychological impact of such policies.

This analysis reveals that diaspora engagement, while potentially transformative for migration governance systems, remains constrained by structural and epistemological limitations. The case studies demonstrate how current frameworks often reduce MO/DOs to functional actors within predetermined policy architectures rather than recognizing them as co-constructors of mobility regimes. At its core, the tension between return governance and diaspora participation exposes a fundamental paradox: the expectation of migrant communities to legitimize systems that frequently marginalize their epistemic and political agency. These findings challenge prevailing migration governance paradigms by situating return policies within broader theorizations of mobility justice (Sheller 2018), where technical solutions inevitably falter when decoupled from structural transformations. Future research must further interrogate how diasporic knowledge production might reconfigure the very foundations of migration governance beyond its current state-centric imaginary.

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